

Schmidt Ocean Institute Post Expedition Report

Hydrothermal Vents of the Western Galápagos

Chief Scientist Dr. Roxanne Beinart

Co-Chief Scientist: Jill McDermott

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1 Overview

SOI Expedition ID	FKt230812
Vessel	R/V <i>Falkor (too)</i>
Expedition Name	Hydrothermal Vents of the Western Galápagos
Expedition Dates	2023/08/13 - 2023/09/10
Departure Port	Balboa, Panama
Termination Port	Puerto Ayora, Ecuador
Ocean	North Pacific Ocean

Figure 1: Map of Expedition Location.

1.1 Expedition Overview

Hydrothermal vents were discovered in 1977 along the Eastern Galápagos Spreading Center (EGSC), about 250 miles from the Galápagos Islands. Since the discovery, these hydrothermal vents all around the world have been studied for the biology, chemistry, and geology of these unique seafloor ecosystems. Past research has enabled significant advances in knowledge of the limits of life, Earth's internal geological processes, and oceans chemistry.

This expedition comprised an interdisciplinary team composed of researchers from six institutions. In collaboration with the Charles Darwin Foundation, the Galápagos National Park, and the local navy, the team sailed west of the Galápagos Islands with the goals of finding, investigating, and characterizing the underexplored and unknown vents in the area.

1.2 Authorizations and Permitting

Permit Number	Permit Authority	Permit Focus
005-2023	INOCAR	Authorization for entry of Foreign Flag Vessels
PC-51-23	Parque Nacional Galápagos	Scientific Research

1.3 Expedition Timeline

The expedition began on August 13, 2023, departing from Balboa, Panama, and concluded in Puerto Ayora, Ecuador, on September 10, 2023.

1.4 Expedition Objectives

The research team aimed to explore three known areas of hydrothermal venting, called Iguanas, Pingüinos, and Navidad, and to locate and explore two additional areas, which were previously suspected based on the detection of a chemical signature that is unique to vents in the water above. Previous expeditions to Iguanas, Pingüinos, and Navidad vent fields found lush symbiotic animal communities dominated by giant tubeworms, clams, and mussels that are similar to those along the EGSC, as well as unique biology, such as abundant yellow skate eggs incubating in warm venting fluid. At the Western Galápagos Spreading Center (WGSC), the team further surveyed the animal and microbial biodiversity of these sites, with the ultimate goal of using genetic and taxonomic methods to identify them, and compare them to communities and populations at the EGSC.

2 Expedition Accomplishments

2.1 At-sea Accomplishments

The expedition started at the Iguanas vent field, for a series of three ROV dives (Aug. 18-22). Then proceeded to a nearby vent field, Pinguinos, for two dives (Aug. 22-24). Next, the cruise transited to a site previously suspected to have hydrothermal venting, called 93.7W/DSL2A, where the team performed tow-yos with the CTD to locate vent plume signatures and then ultimately dove with the ROV on Aug. 25. The team was able to find active venting at this site

and then continued on to Navidad, a site previously only seen by towed cameras, and did a series of three dives (though one was aborted) from Aug. 27-30. The cruise then moved to the second site, where hydrothermal plume signatures had been previously detected (called 94.4W/DSL2b) and did tow-yos with the CTD for 35 hours (Table 3). A final dive on that site was conducted on Aug. 31 and ultimately led to the discovery of the hydrothermal venting source after approximately 40 hours of searching with the ROV. Two additional dives were conducted at this new site, informally named, Sendero del Cangrejo. The team then backtracked the cruise path and ended the cruise with three more dives at Iguanas from Sept. 5 through Sept 9. Figure 2, Table 1, and Table 2 present the dive site location, metadata, and the number of collected samples at each location, respectively

Figure 2: Fkt230812 Dive locations.

Table 1: ROV *SuBastian* Dive Metadata.

ROV Dive ID	Location	Total Dive Time	Max Depth	Launch Date	Lat	Lon
S0562	Iguanas	00d 22:46:44	1696.08m	18 August 2023	2.107384	-91.938257
S0563	Iguanas	00d 21:30:41	1698.99m	19 August 2023	2.1055144	-91.9265871
S0564	Iguanas	01d 02:35:20	1699.98m	21 August 2023	2.105188	-91.926285
S0565	Pinguinos	00d 20:04:02	1710.77m	22 August 2023	2.099464	-91.905086
S0566	Pinguinos	00d 18:02:37	1700.19m	24 August 2023	2.100233	-91.905025
S0567	93.7W (DSL2a) Site	01d 00:52:05	2406.5m	25 August 2023	2.494454	-93.696904
S0568	Navidad	01d 01:42:55	2445.19m	27 August 2023	2.526815	-94.076392
S0569	Navidad (aborted)	00d 01:34:00	14.14m	28 August 2023	n/a	n/a
S0570	Navidad	01d 11:24:45	2454.67m	28 August 2023	2.525903	-94.069587
S0571	Sendero del Cangrejo	01d 19:25:00	2535.98m	31 August 2023	2.543348	-94.376169
S0572	Sendero del Cangrejo	00d 18:18:03	2509.37m	3 September 2023	2.53113	-94.355408
S0573	Sendero del Cangrejo	00d 16:59:15	2504.3m	4 September 0202	2.53191	-94.3586
S0574	Iguanas	00d 08:25:51	1677.55m	5 September 2023	2.104018	-91.927085
S0575	Iguanas	01d 02:31:08	1702.2m	7 September 2023	2.103922 3	-91.926581
S0576	Iguanas	00d 22:16:29	2445.19m	9 September 2023	2.10506,	-91.93776

Table 2: ROV *SuBastian* sample collection overview. Number of each sample type per dive is shown.

ROV Dive ID	Location	Biological Collections	Rock Collections	Sediment Push Cores	Isobaric Gas Tight Samples	Microbial samples (SUPR)	Niskin water samples for eDNA (ROV)
S0562	Iguanas	5	8	2	4	9	3
S0563	Iguanas	2	7	1	4	12	3
S0564	Iguanas	3	5	2	4	8	3
S0565	Pinguinos	3	6	0	4	6	3
S0566	Pinguinos	4	8	0	4	3	4
S0567	93.7W (DSL2 a) site	1	0	2	0	0	0
S0568	Navidad	4	9	0	4	8	4
S0569	Navidad - aborted	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	0
S0570	Navidad	9	8	4	4	14	3
S0571	Sendero del Cangrejo	4	8	6	4	7	3
S0572	Sendero del Cangrejo	4	1	0	4	5	3
S0573	Sendero del Cangrejo	2	6	3	4	7	0
S0574	Iguanas	1	1	3	4	0	0
S0575	Iguanas	7	5	3	4	8	3
S0576	Iguanas	1	3	4	4	10	3
	Sum	50	75	30	52	97	35

Table 3: CTD cast and tow-yo metadata.

CTD ID	Location	Start (ts)	End (ts)	Duration (hrs)	Notes
CTD_001	Background (non-vent) near Pinguinos	2023-08-18T14:35:18.585Z	2023-08-18T16:38:24.782Z	2.07	Background (non-vent) water for IGTs near Pinguinos
CTD_002	Pinguinos	2023-08-24T03:39:14.000Z	2023-08-24T06:57:48.664Z	3.3	Pinguinos, questionable vent plume
CTD_003	93.7W/DSL2A	2023-08-25T14:37:48.019Z	Not recorded (estimated 2023-08-26T06:43:59.483Z)	~16.1	Tow-Yo, searching for vent plume
CTD_004	94.4W/DSL2B (Sendero del Cangrejo)	2023-08-30T17:10:58.745Z	Not recorded (estimated 2023-09-01T05:10:37.943Z)	~35.99	Tow-Yo, searching for vent plume

CTD ID	Location	Start (ts)	End (ts)	Duration (hrs)	Notes
CTD_005	94.4W/DSL2B (Sendero del Cangrejo)	2023-09-04T02:48:25.000Z	2023-09-04T06:11:45.594Z	3.38	Likely vent plume
CTD_006	Iguanas	2023-09-08T23:53:49.308Z	2023-09-09T01:44:52.243Z	1.85	Likely vent plume

2.1.1 Science

2.1.1.1 Bathymetric Mapping

Shipboard sonar (Kongsberg EM124 and EM712) was used to provide bathymetry basemaps to guide operations and was used to acquire data during transits to fill data gaps in publicly available data compilations, including GMRT and Seabed 2030. A total of 18,680 km² of bathymetry data were acquired, which can be gridded into data products at a variety of resolutions based on water depth and ship speed. An overview map of all ship-based multibeam data is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Extent of ship-based multibeam sonar data acquired during FKt230812.

2.1.1.2 Near-bottom bathymetry surveys

The near-bottom M3 multibeam sonar was acquired during dives S0570 - S0576. The system was not installed on the ROV during dives S0562 - S0567; testing and calibration was performed during S0568, and dive S0569 was aborted during launch. Acquisition of bathymetry data at each site visited is described in Table 4. The M3 multibeam worked well overall and the navigation from *SuBastian* was easily integrated post-dive to generate bathymetry maps to inform operations rapidly.

Table 4: Near-bottom bathymetric data acquired with ROV *SuBastian* during FKt230812

Site	Dive(s)	Area Mapped (m ²)	Summary
Navidad	S0570	73,388	Imaged vent field revealing details of seafloor morphology not previously identifiable.
Sendero del Cangrejo	S0571, S0572, S0573	221,020	Collected a lot of data while hunting for a vent field. Vent structures are not clearly identifiable in bathymetry.
Iguanas-East	S0574, S0575	32,439	Surveyed over DTS lander and over known vent sites.
Iguanas-West	S0575, S0576	36,836	Acquired higher resolution data than previously existed revealing vent structures

2.1.1.2.1 Navidad

Near-bottom bathymetry data was acquired during one dive at Navidad. This site was previously mapped with the DSL120 which did not provide detailed bathymetry data. The resulting 0.5 m resolution grid clearly imaged 4 hydrothermal structures (~5m tall) that are oriented parallel to the primary E-W trending fault and are aligned along a fissure.

Figure 4: 3D oblique view of 0.5 m resolution bathymetry at Navidad. White flags indicate areas of venting. Water depths ranged from -2408 to -2452.

2.1.1.2.2 Sendero del Cangrejo

Mapping at this site was largely exploratory guided by tow-yo data. Previous bathymetry data was acquired with the DSL120 but did not reveal sufficient details to identify areas of venting. Due to the exploratory nature of this dive, it yielded more data coverage than at other sites, and survey altitude was highly variable as the ROV ascended and descended frequently during exploration. The seafloor at this site is much more complex with a series of parallel faults. Hydrothermal vent structures are not easily identifiable in these maps.

Figure 5: Image collected by *SuBastian* at 0.5 m resolution bathymetry data at Sendero del Cangrejo overlain on top of pre-existing DSL120 data. Water depths ranged from -2475 to -2528 m.

2.1.1.2.3 Iguanas

Previously acquired near-bottom data at Iguanas (*Sentry* ~1m resolution) was used to guide most activities at both Iguanas-East and Iguanas-West. A small area of Iguanas-East was mapped with the M3 on *SuBastian* (altitude 10m) and was focused around the location of the DTS lander. The resulting 0.5 m resolution grid covers an area of 0.03 km² and includes multiple areas of active venting. Three 6-10m tall smokers are perched atop a 15m fault scarp and one chimlet (~2m tall) was identified ~60m from the base of the scarp. A fissure with evidence of venting was located between these structures. Bathymetry data at Iguanas-West was a bit more limited but still revealed several vent structures ranging in height from 8-12 m were identified along a fault scarp that has a throw ranging from 10 to 20 m. The chimneys identified in the M3 bathymetry data at both Iguanas-East and Iguanas-West were not visible in the *Sentry* data.

Figure 6: Image of Iguanas-East *SuBastian* 0.5 m resolution bathymetry data overlain on top of *Sentry* 1-m bathymetry data. Water depths ranged from -1630 to -1710 m.

Figure 7: Image of Iguanas-West *SuBastian* 0.5 m resolution bathymetry data overlain on top of *Sentry* 1-m bathymetry data. White flags indicate areas of active venting. Water depths ranged from -1655 to -1712 m.

2.1.1.3 Biology

2.1.1.3.1 eDNA sampling

The biodiversity surveys were enhanced by the collection of environmental DNA (eDNA) data. Environmental DNA collects shed animal cells and tissues from the environment to detect a broad spectrum of animals present in the area, including those that we cannot see or sample directly. The research team will also use data from our animal and microbial collections to look for genetic similarities between Western and Eastern Galapagos Spreading Center animal populations, which will help us to better characterize how animals disperse and travel between venting areas. Given that two of the sites fell within the protected area of the Galápagos Marine Reserve, a better understanding of the animals and microbes inhabiting them and how they are connected to other hydrothermal areas in the region will be critical for their management and conservation.

In addition to comparisons with the EGSC, hydrothermal vents along the WGSC present a special opportunity to study the geologic processes controlling hydrothermal vents chemistry and mineral composition that are influenced by hot spot volcanism. Volcanoes are only found in certain places on Earth. The WGSC is one such volcanic area, as it aligns with the boundary of two diverging tectonic plates, the rigid outer layers of the Earth that 'float' on top of the more-dense mantle layer. "Hotspot" volcanoes are a second type of volcano that can form in the middle of a plate. The WGSC is a complex area because there is a divergent plate boundary very close to a hotspot volcano centered on the Galápagos Islands. The presence of this hotspot causes the seafloor depth to deepen and the oceanic crust to thin from east to west in this area. Physical differences like these, as well as chemical differences in the erupted lavas, could impact the resulting chemistry and mineralogy of the hydrothermal vents from Pingüinos to Iguanas to Navidad, away from the peak hotspot influence at the Galápagos Islands. Here, the research team used high-resolution multibeam mapping to survey the bathymetry (topography) of the hydrothermal areas, sampled rocks, and hydrothermal deposits to analyze mineralogy and used specialized, high-pressure fluid samplers (isobaric gas tights) that will allowed for the collection and measurement of the chemicals in venting fluid, like methane, hydrogen, and metals.

2.1.1.3.2 Animal Sampling

Benthic Animal Sampling

The objectives of benthic macrofaunal collections were to record the diversity and distribution of hydrothermal vent communities in the Western Galapagos and to sample target species for DNA sequencing and biochemical measurements (**Table A1**). This will allow the research team to establish a comprehensive barcode reference library for hydrothermal vent fauna, assess the population structure of animals and their microbial symbionts within the WGSC and in relation to other regions, and better understand the physiology of these unique fauna. Animals were collected by ROV *SuBastian* via faunal grabs, slurps, and opportunistically from rocks collected for geology. Epifauna were collected by sieving water from bioboxes with a mesh net. Specimens were sorted by morphology and most were photographed with a Sony A7III full-frame mirrorless camera equipped with a Nikon AF Micro Nikkor 105mm f/2.8 Macro lens. Samples for genetic work were either flash frozen and stored at -80°C or were preserved in salt-saturated 20% DMSO (Dimethyl Sulfoxide), RNAlater, or 70% EtOH. Samples of symbiont-

containing tissues for morphological and microscopic examination were preserved in paraformaldehyde or glutaraldehyde. Calcifying fluid was collected from some bivalves. All samples either had a whole animal or tissue duplicate preserved in 95%EtOH for the Charles Darwin Foundation (CDF). Voucher specimens were also preserved in 95%EtOH and remain in the possession of CDF. A total of 45 species were observed and 8 species were documented in this region for the first time: *Alvinella caudata*, *Cyananthea hydrothermala*, *Eulepetopsis vitrea*, *Hesiolyra bergi*, *Lepidonotopodium fimbriatum* (**Fig.8**), *Peltospira* sp., *Sericosura* sp., and *Thermonemertes valens* (**Fig.8**).

Observed Taxa

***Bolded text indicates the first observation at Galapagos Spreading Center region**

<i>Actinostola</i> sp.	Crinoid	Ophiuroid
<i>Alvinella caudata</i>	<i>Cyanagraea praedator</i>	<i>Cyananthea hydrothermala</i>
<i>Alvinella pompejana</i>	<i>Galapagomystides artista</i>	<i>Eulepetopsis vitrea</i>
<i>Alvinocaris lusca</i>	<i>Haleciid hydroid</i>	<i>Paragorgia</i> sp.
<i>Amphisamytha galapagensis</i>	<i>Hesiolyra bergi</i>	<i>Paralvinella grasslei</i>
<i>Archinome rosacea</i>	<i>Hesiospina vestimifera</i>	<i>Peltospira</i> sp.
<i>Bathymodiolus thermophilus</i>	<i>Isidid coral (bamboo)</i>	<i>Phymorhynchus major</i>
<i>Bathyraja abyssicola</i>	<i>Laminatubus alvini</i>	<i>Prionospio sandersi</i>
<i>Branchinotogluma sandersi</i>	<i>Lepetodrilus cristatus</i>	<i>Riftia pachyptila</i>
<i>Branchipolynoe symmytilida</i>	<i>Lepetodrilus elevatus</i>	<i>Scalpellid barnacle</i>
<i>Bythograea</i> sp.	<i>Lepetodrilus pustulosus</i>	<i>Sericosura</i> sp.
<i>Bythograea thermydron</i>	<i>Lepidonotopodium fimbriatum</i>	<i>Teonia jerichoana</i>
<i>Calyptogena magnifica</i>	<i>Nereimyra alvinae</i>	<i>Thermonemertes valens</i>
<i>Chirostyloidid</i>	<i>Nereis sandersi</i>	<i>Ventiella sulfuris</i>
<i>Cladorizid sponge</i>	<i>Nodopelta</i> sp.	<i>Zoanthi</i>

Figure 8: Voucher photographs of selected newly-observed species at Galapagos Spreading Center observed during this cruise. (left to right) *Thermonemertes valens* and *Lepidonotopodium fimbriatum*.

Pelagic Ctenophore Sampling

The Ctenophora, also known as comb jellies, are a globally ubiquitous but sparsely described (~250 species) group of marine invertebrates that were recently found to be human's most distant animal relatives, having branched off from other animals even before sea sponges. They are also of interest in studying open-ocean genetic connectivity and adaptation to pressure and cold in the deep sea. Three benthic ctenophores were collected during ROV transits and ten pelagic specimens were suction-sampled during ascents. Of the thirteen total specimens, four are likely undescribed species and one is of indeterminate genus. All sampled ctenophores are listed in **Table 5**. Most specimens were photographed (e.g. **Fig. 9**), DNA samples were preserved for molecular phylogenetics, and bulk tissues were frozen at -80°C to analyze pressure-adaptation of the cell membranes.

Figure 9: Three pelagic ctenophores collected during ascent. Both *Bathocyroe* images at bottom are of the same specimen.

Table 5: Ctenophores collected as a survey of genetic and physiological diversity.

Dive number	Sample ID	Class	ID	Remarks
S0565	SS1	Cydippida	<i>Vampyroctena</i> sp.	
S0566	SS2	Cydippida	<i>Duobrachium</i> sp.	Benthic cydippid
S0568	SS1	Lobata	<i>Lampocteis</i> sp.	Amber color
S0570	SS1	Beroida	<i>Beroe</i> aff. <i>abyssicola</i>	
S0570	SS3	Lobata	<i>Bathocyroe</i> aff. <i>Fosteri</i>	
S0570	SS4	Cydippida	<i>Hormiphora</i> sp.	
S0570	SS5	Cydippida	Unknown mertensiid	
S0572	CQ2A	Platyctenida	Unknown platyctene	Benthic with red-pigmented gut
S0572	CQ2B	Platyctenida	Unknown platyctene	Benthic with red-pigmented gut
S0574	SS1	Beroida	<i>Beroe forskalii</i>	
S0575	SS1	Lobata	<i>Kiyohimea</i> aff. <i>usagi</i>	
S0575	SS2	Cydippida	Unknown cydippid, orange gut	
S0576	SS5	Cydippida	<i>Aulacoctena</i> sp.	

2.2 Post-expedition Activities and Accomplishments

2.2.1 Overview

eDNA sampling

Environmental DNA (eDNA) is the genetic material that marine organisms release into the surrounding water. eDNA undergoes degradation or settles to the benthos. Prior to degradation or settling, it can be captured by filtering seawater and subsequently isolated and sequenced in a laboratory setting. The sequencing of eDNA has proven to be an effective technique for evaluating biodiversity in the ocean, with application to deep-sea research. eDNA sampling during this cruise was collected to test the utility of using water sampling for assessing hydrothermal vent animal communities and supplements similar samples taken with HOV Alvin at East Pacific Rise 9° 50'N in January 2023.

Niskin Samples

To obtain eDNA samples that captured the surrounding community, Niskin samples were collected by ROV *SuBastian* within three meters of animal aggregations and obtained before biological collections to limit capturing an unnatural abundance of DNA in the water column (**Fig.10**). Immediately after ROV recovery, water from the Niskin bottles was filtered over a Smith Root filter capsule with a 5.0µm pore-size polyethersulfone membrane. The entire volume of the sample was gravity filtered within 15 minutes. Filters were removed from

capsules and preserved in Longmire's Buffer Solution and stored at room temperature until genetic analysis. A total of 33 Niskin eDNA samples were collected for genetic analyses (Table A2) with 2-3 replicates per sampling event.

Figure 10: Niskin eDNA sampling method. Water is gravity filtered from the 5L Niskin bottles located on the port side of ROV *SuBastian* using Smith Root filter capsules with 5.0µm pore-size polyethersulfone membrane filter.

Microbial sampling with SUPR

The Suspended Particulate Rosette (SUPR) sampler (Mclane Research Laboratories, Inc.) was mounted on ROV *Subastian* to sample microbial populations and eDNA in the environment. Up to 14 142-mm diameter Millipore Express Plus 0.2 micron filters (with custom nylon mesh 10 micron prefilters from Sefar, Inc.) were deployed each dive. See Table A3 for SUPR sample information and metadata.

Microbial sampling of hydrothermal sulfides

Hydrothermal sulfides banked for ship- and shore-based incubation and metabolism measurements, metagenomics and metatranscriptomics, and community lipidomics

Hydrothermal massive sulfides host extreme thermal and redox gradients, and these are known in turn to host microbes. Much remains unknown, however, about the spatial distribution,

metabolic activities, and biochemical adaptations of these communities, due to material limitations and the analytical methods historically available.

Hydrothermal sulfide samples were collected from active vent fields by ROV *SuBastian*, photo-documented shipboard, and subsequently prepared according to downstream analytical needs (Table 6). “Live” sulfides – samples that were not preserved by freezing or preservative solution – they were stored at 4°C in sulfidic, anoxic seawater (500 μM [HS⁻]; 28 mM [SO₄²⁻], ~2 mM DIC; pH 6.5) produced using a gas dissolution equilibration column inside the mobile lab van (Fig. 11). Previous work has shown that these conditions preserve the viability of many endemic microbes, including thermophiles. These samples can be “revived” in a shore-based laboratory and used to repeat experiments like described below. In addition to “live” samples, large sulfide samples (Table 6) were frozen at -80°C for later subsampling, genetic, and lipidomic analysis. A split of each sample was retained by Dr. Amy Gartman’s research group for mineralogical analysis, which will provide temperature constraints for various layers of the chimney wall. Finally, a subset of sulfides were preserved in situ at the seafloor by dropping samples into stoppered coral quivers on the deck of the ROV *SuBastian* containing RNA preservative solution (a.k.a. “RNAlater”; 0.5 M EDTA, 1 M Na₃C₆H₅O₇, 5.31 M (NH₄)₂SO₄, pH 8.0). Because RNAlater is denser than seawater, when coral quivers were opened at the seafloor to add samples, RNAlater was not lost to mixing with bottom water but rather stayed inside the coral quiver. Once samples were added to each quiver, the lid was restoppered to keep the sample preserved for the duration of the dive. Upon retrieval at the surface, contents of each coral quiver (rocks and RNAlater) were transferred to Ziploc bags and left to have RNAlater saturate the sample overnight at 4°C. These samples will be processed for DNA and RNA recovery, which, in turn, will be sequenced to generate metagenomic and metatranscriptomic libraries to document the microbial communities and their metabolic activities as they were preserved in situ at the time of sample collection, thereby minimizing potential biases that could result from depressurization of samples during ascent to the surface.

Table 6: Hydrothermal sulfide samples collected for microbiology work. A total of five active structures were sampled at Iguanas, Pinguinos, Navidad, and Sendero del Cangrejo vent fields.

Dive number	Vent Field	Sulfide Type	Sample ID
S0562	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R01
S0562	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R02A
S0562	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R02B
S0562	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R02C
S0562	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R02D
S0562	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R03
S0563	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R01
S0564	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R01A
S0564	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R01B.1
S0564	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R01B.2
S0564	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R01C
S0564	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R01C.1
S0564	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R01C.2
S0564	Iguanas	Active Chimney	R01D

Dive number	Vent Field	Sulfide Type	Sample ID
S0565	Pinguinos	Active Chimney	R03B
S0565	Pinguinos	Active Chimney	R03B.1
S0565	Pinguinos	Active Chimney	R03B.2
S0565	Pinguinos	Active Chimney	R03B.3
S0565	Pinguinos	Active Chimney	R03C
S0566	Pinguinos	Standing inactive	R01B
S0566	Pinguinos	Active Chimney	R02
S0566	Pinguinos	Active Chimney	R03
S0566	Pinguinos	Active Chimney	R06
S0566	Pinguinos	Talus	R07
S0566	Pinguinos	Active Chimney	R08
S0568	Navidad	Active Chimney	R02C
S0568	Navidad	Small active mini flange from "pagoda" formation.	R03B
S0568	Navidad	Inactive flange from "pagoda" formation	R05
S0568	Navidad	Standing Inactive	R06B
S0570	Navidad	Active chimney	R04B
S0570	Navidad	Small flange from "pagoda" formation.	R07
S0570	Navidad	Active Chimney	R08
S0571	Sendero del cangrejo	Active Chimney	R07
S0571	Sendero del cangrejo	Active Chimney	R08B.1
S0571	Sendero del cangrejo	Active Chimney	R08B.2
S0571	Sendero del cangrejo	Active Chimney	R08B.3
S0571	Sendero del cangrejo	Active Chimney	R08B.4
S0571	Sendero del cangrejo	Active Chimney	R08C

Anaerobic oxidation of methane (AOM) enrichment cultures of a hydrothermal sulfide at controlled temperature and pressure

Due to the coincident thermal and redox gradients that occur in hydrothermal chimney walls, it has been challenging to isolate the effects of temperature, pressure, and fluid chemistry on the metabolism of microbes inhabiting these structures. To quantify temperature and pressure effects, incubations were performed under different pressure-temperature regimes (Fig. 11) with sulfidic seawater (described above) spiked with ^{13}C -methane ($250 \mu\text{M}$) and ^{15}N -ammonium ($100 \mu\text{M}$) designed to enrich for anaerobic oxidation of methane (AOM) coupled to sulfate reduction. For each sample, ~ 10 g of active vent sample from Iguanas (S0562-R02) was homogenized into a sedimented slurry at 4°C inside an anoxic glove bag sparged with N_2 gas. Prepared slurries were quickly transferred into gas-tight mylar bags, filled to a final volume of 35 mL sulfidic seawater containing heavy isotope tracers, heat-sealed, and then incubated shipboard at either 1 bar or 165 bar (i.e., seafloor pressure at the Iguanas site where S0562-R02 was collected). Four temperature conditions – 4°C , 20°C , 65°C , or 90°C – were assessed at each pressure, and enrichments were incubated for 10 days. For each condition, a total of 4 bio-

replicates and one formalin-fixed kill control were incubated for a total of 10 days. Dissolved gas concentrations were achieved for each temperature/pressure combination using the Ideal Gas Law and Henry's Law.

Figure 11: Pressure/temperature-controlled sulfide incubations. A illustrates the experimental design with 2 pressures, 4 temperatures, and N=4 replicates per condition plus 1 killed control. B shows one of the stainless steel pressure vessels used.

At both $T = 0$ and $T = 10$ days, the pH was measured using a pH probe and aliquots were taken for aqueous geochemistry. For each sample, 1.1 mL of slurry was aliquoted for [DIC] and ^{13}C DIC, to which 100 μL saturated HgCl_2 was added to arrest biological activity and prevent additional isotopic fractionation post-incubation. Another 5 mL aliquot was collected from each sample for [HS⁻] measurements, with sulfide being base trapped in solution (and biological activity arrested) by adding 2N Zn-acetate buffered with 1N NaOH to a final concentration of 5% (v/v).

After sample collection for aqueous geochemistry, 10 mL of slurry was collected from each bio-replicate and allocated to a "central pool" for that condition (40 mL total per pool; kill controls were not included). The mixture was homogenized by gentle pipetting and then 20 mL were filtered through a 0.2 μm Sterivex filter to collect biomass. Nucleic acids were preserved by flushing each Sterivex filter with homemade RNA preservative solution, leaving to quench overnight at 4°C before transferring to -30°C freezers for the remainder of the cruise. The remaining 20 mL of each condition's "central pool" was centrifuged for 10 min at 3000 $\times g$ in preparation for fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH). Following centrifugation, media was decanted and samples were fixed in 2% (v/v) paraformaldehyde (PFA) in filter-sterilized seawater overnight at 4°C. The next morning, fixed samples were centrifuged for 10 min at 3000 $\times g$, the PFA poured off, and samples were washed thrice with 1 \times phosphate buffered saline (PBS). Following washing, samples were subjected to an ethanol dehydration series (50%, 70%,

90%, 100% v/v) and then stored in 50 mL Falcon tubes at 4°C with a 100% (v/v) ethanol-soaked kimwipe. Remaining solids (i.e. sediment slurries) from the incubation experiments were frozen at -80°C for complementary downstream lipidomics. The sample suite is described in **Table 6**.

Habitat Mapping

Quantifying the distribution limits of benthic communities at and near hydrothermal vents can help us understand the physical and chemical conditions that constrain their presence, health, and function in the deep-sea. Hydrothermal vent fauna occurs along a temperature gradient from vent fluid to ambient seawater with zones corresponding to the visually-dominant fauna. Observations of invertebrates that live near hydrothermal vents are usually biased to where they occur due to limited seafloor bottom time on dives. In shallower environments, quantitative estimates of marine fauna distribution and biomass typically rely on quadrat or transect surveys (e.g., photoquadrats in coral reefs), and the goal with these ROV video transects was to replicate the statistical power in unbiased observations for deep-sea fauna. To establish the distribution extent of different vent communities in the Western Galápagos Spreading Center we conducted biological video transects on dives using ROV *SuBastian*. The transects were used to reduce observation bias and provide still images that could be processed to estimate biomass and species presence.

Methods

Using ROV *SuBastian* and its science camera, a SULIS Subsea Z70 shooting in 4K and with 12X zoom, video transects were taken at 0.2 to 0.3 m/s along straight paths from 2.5 to 4 m above the seafloor. The largest vent fields were ~300 m so transects usually took 25-30 min to traverse a field at this speed. Consistently keeping the lasers on for scale and maintaining the same camera angle, zoom level, ROV speed, pitch, roll, etc. created the best transect video for analysis and comparison later. The transect paths varied depending on the situation and opportunity but almost always involved collecting footage from a hydrothermal fluid or vent source to the habitat extent (see **Fig. 12** for an example of the first transect at Iguanas). Typically, the ROV traveled across a vent field with a fluid source at the center to the habitat extent and occasionally traveled up a steep cliff with fauna or up chimneys.

Preliminary results

Transects were performed on six separate dives covering about 1400 m of seafloor at four different hydrothermal vent fields (Iguanas, Pinguinos, Navidad, and the newly named Sendero del Cangrejo). **Table 7** displays relevant information for all of the transects with location, depth, start and end time, distance covered, and notes. As of yet, no further analyses have been performed using the video footage but analysis will start this year in Andrew Davies' lab at U. Rhode Island.

Figure 12: Example of the biological video transect path on dive S0564 at Chimlet 1 (orange triangle) in the Iguanas vent field on 22 Aug 2023 starting with a N-S transect first away from Chimlet 1 and then back towards after reaching the habitat periphery, and then a different N-E transect to the extent and back. The gray area represents the habitat surrounding Chimlet 1.

Table 7: Dives where transects were performed with hydrothermal vent field, start and end time, estimated total distance covered, lat and lon of the general area (from SealogSample information), approximate depth, and relevant notes.

Dive #	Vent Field	Start (UTC)	End (UTC)	Distance covered (m)	Lat (ddeg)	Lon (ddeg)	Depth (m)	Notes
S0564	Iguanas	2023-08-22 10:20:00	2023-08-22 12:24:00	300	2.103304	-91.92665	1660	Combined transect with Distributed Temperature Sensor (DTS) deployment
S0565	Pinguinos	2023-08-23 22:27:00	2023-08-23 22:57:00	450	2.100793	-91.905892	1690	SuPR during and after the transect; do not currently have the video for this transect on Davies lab servers
S0570	Navidad	2023-08-30 5:00:00	2023-08-30 7:24:00	280	2.527279	-94.075484	2400	It was not one consistent transect during this time, the first one finished around 5:44 and the second one started around 6:48; the video collected comprises this entire time, though.
S0573	Sendero del Cangrejo	2023-09-04 19:20:00	2023-09-04 19:58:00	110	2.531672	-94.358556	2490	Went up and down a 15m tall chimney; <i>Riftia pachyptila</i> ; traveled to habitat extents; the lasers appeared not perfectly calibrated from this dive on
S0575	Iguanas	2023-09-08 19:41:00	2023-09-08 20:18:00	100	2.1045	-91.92553	1660	Performed a cross or X with Smoker 7 in the center passing Mussels 3 and Mussel bed on the way; there was a lot of trouble on this transect with navigational issues (the map scale seemed to be off and the ROV pilots tried their best to fix it and get a transect); saw skate eggs at 20:17
S0576	Iguanas	2023-09-09 22:15:00	2023-09-09 22:45:00	155	2.104831	-91.938109	1660	Part of a longer transect to travel as far north as possible for a push core away from the rift starting at Smoker 4 (which was hard to find exact coordinates of), dubbed 'Amy's (Gartman) Last Transect'; ended at 155 m to go faster

Vent Fluid Geochemical Sampling

In total, 47 vent fluid samples were successfully collected with isobaric gas-tight (IGT) samplers and processed onboard. Vent fluids were collected from 20 high temperature vents and 5 low temperature vent orifices across the vent fields including Iguanas, Pinguinos, Navidad, and Sendero del Cangrejo.

There are four main objectives for the geochemical analyses from vent fluid samples collected on this cruise: (1) estimate the maximum pressure and temperature of fluid formation using the chemistry of major ions and trace metals in the hottest ‘source’ hydrothermal vent fluids at each vent field, (2) investigate the relationship between high-temperature hydrothermal fluid compositions and distance from the Galapagos hotspot center, (3) quantify the chemical energy sources available to micro-organisms at a diversity of ‘diffuse’ venting locations where hydrothermal fluids mix with seawater across a spectrum of temperature regimes, and (4), we constrain magmatic inputs and fluid residence time in the oceanic crust using radiocarbon and stable carbon analysis of total dissolved inorganic carbon, coupled to helium abundance and isotopic analysis.

Fluid temperatures were monitored continuously during sample collection using a thermocouple aligned with the sampler snorkel inlet on each IGT sampler. For each fluid sample, the maximum measured temperature ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) observed during collection is reported in Table 8. During sample processing, aliquots were extracted for immediate shipboard analysis of pH (25°C) and dissolved $\Sigma\text{H}_2\text{S}$ ($\Sigma\text{H}_2\text{S} = \text{H}_2\text{S} + \text{HS}^- + \text{S}_2^-$), CH_4 and H_2 . Fluid pH (25°C , 1 atm) was measured by potentiometry using a Ag / AgCl combination reference electrode standardized at pH 4 and pH 7. Dissolved H_2 and CH_4 were analyzed by gas chromatography (GC) using a 5A° molecular sieve packed column and thermal conductivity detection after headspace extraction in a glass gastight syringe. Dissolved $\Sigma\text{H}_2\text{S}$ was determined shipboard via shipboard analysis by iodometric starch titration of an aliquot drawn into a gastight syringe. Additional aliquots were preserved for shore-based $\Sigma\text{H}_2\text{S}$ as Ag_2S in 5 wt% AgNO_3 for later gravimetric determination in the shore-based laboratory at Lehigh University. The refractive index at 25°C and 1 bar in parts per thousand units is reported, a value that is analogous to fluid salinity at standard conditions.

In addition to shipboard analysis, additional aliquots were collected and preserved for later shore-based determination of: major ions, minor and trace metals, ΣCO_2 abundance, stable isotopes and radiocarbon isotopes, CH_4 and C_2+ alkane abundance via GIC-flame ionization detection, oxygen and deuterium isotopes on water, helium abundance and isotopes, and nutrients including ΣNH_3 and PO_4^{3-} .

Table 8: Metadata for isobaric gas tight (IGT) samples

Dive	Vent Site	Sample ID	Tmax ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Lat (dd)	Long (dd)	Water Depth (m)	Timestamp (UTC)
S0562	Iguanas	S562-IGT1	236	2.104388	-91.936306	1656	2023-08-19T11:47:18.987Z
S0562	Iguanas	S562-IGT2	256	2.104410	-91.936319	1656	2023-08-19T12:12:19.615Z
S0562	Iguanas	S562-IGT4	304	2.104333	-91.936302	1648	2023-08-19T18:28:44.853Z
S0562	Iguanas	S562-IGT3	304	2.104331	-91.936302	1648	2023-08-19T19:05:46.483Z

Dive	Vent Site	Sample ID	Tmax (°C)	Lat (dd)	Long (dd)	Water Depth (m)	Timestamp (UTC)
S0563	Iguanas	S563-IGT1	261	2.103999	-91.926539	1668	2023-08-20T14:28:13.984Z
S0563	Iguanas	S563-IGT2	260	2.104022	-91.926526	1668	2023-08-20T14:54:27.617Z
S0563	Iguanas	S563-IGT3	331	2.104943	-91.926279	1644	2023-08-20T21:36:16.078Z
S0563	Iguanas	S563-IGT4	335	2.104944	-91.926276	1644	2023-08-20T21:48:29.663Z
S0564	Iguanas	S564-IGT2	292	2.104016	-91.926512	1668	2023-08-21T21:41:28.884Z
S0564	Iguanas	S564-IGT3	285	2.104331	-91.925523	1665	2023-08-22T04:13:39.647Z
S0564	Iguanas	S564-IGT4	310	2.104884	-91.926241	1649	2023-08-22T06:58:34.067Z
S0565	Pinguinos	S565-IGT1	203	2.099442	-91.906133	1670	2023-08-23T10:41:37.433Z
S0565	Pinguinos	S565-IGT2	203	2.099444	-91.906131	1670	2023-08-23T11:01:44.283Z
S0565	Pinguinos	S565-IGT3	216	2.099345	-91.906131	1664	2023-08-23T21:40:59.994Z
S0565	Pinguinos	S565-IGT4	216	2.099340	-91.906136	1664	2023-08-23T21:55:48.936Z
S0566	Pinguinos	S566-IGT1	249	2.099293	-91.905474	1671	2023-08-24T16:22:39.534Z
S0566	Pinguinos	S566-IGT2	204	2.099301	-91.905476	1671	2023-08-24T16:47:00.451Z
S0566	Pinguinos	S566-IGT3	45	2.099167	-91.905003	1661	2023-08-24T22:40:19.818Z
S0566	Pinguinos	S566-IGT4	46	2.099225	-91.905026	1661	2023-08-24T22:56:41.306Z
S0568	Navidad	S568-IGT1	307	2.527591	-94.075146	2416	2023-08-28T01:12:30.354Z
S0568	Navidad	S568-IGT2	315	2.527601	-94.075158	2416	2023-08-28T01:23:46.590Z
S0568	Navidad	S568-IGT3	225	2.527235	-94.075465	2422	2023-08-28T06:19:51.754Z
S0568	Navidad	S568-IGT4	228	2.527237	-94.075465	2422	2023-08-28T06:32:33.740Z
S0570	Navidad	S570-IGT1	279	2.527270	-94.076096	2405	2023-08-29T15:23:03.205Z
S0570	Navidad	S570-IGT2	287	2.527274	-94.076096	2405	2023-08-29T15:37:21.676Z
S0570	Navidad	S570-IGT3	15	2.527280	-94.075477	2420	2023-08-30T04:30:03.084Z
S0570	Navidad	S570-IGT4	19	2.527281	-94.075482	2420	2023-08-30T04:49:36.793Z
S0571	Sendero del Cangrejo	S571-IGT1	270	2.531686	-94.358648	2500	2023-09-02T15:36:09.105Z
S0571	Sendero del Cangrejo	S571-IGT2	280	2.531657	-94.358666	2500	2023-09-02T15:50:48.609Z
S0571	Sendero del Cangrejo	S571-IGT3	16	2.531732	-94.358738	2494	2023-09-02T16:35:45.370Z
S0571	Sendero del Cangrejo	S571-IGT4	16	2.531752	-94.358738	2494	2023-09-02T17:01:14.306Z
S0572	Sendero del Cangrejo	S572-IGT1	242	2.531922	-94.359060	2492	2023-09-03T17:37:26.331Z
S0572	Sendero del Cangrejo	S572-IGT2	248	2.531925	-94.359069	2492	2023-09-03T17:55:02.379Z

Dive	Vent Site	Sample ID	Tmax (°C)	Lat (dd)	Long (dd)	Water Depth (m)	Timestamp (UTC)
S0572	Sendero del Cangrejo	S572-IGT3	287	2.531923	-94.358614	2482	2023-09-04T00:14:53.489Z
S0572	Sendero del Cangrejo	S572-IGT4	288	2.531960	-94.358578	2482	2023-09-04T00:25:01.787Z
S0573	Sendero del Cangrejo	S573-IGT1	150	2.531857	-94.358577	2487	2023-09-04T14:51:33.677Z
S0573	Sendero del Cangrejo	S573-IGT2	136	2.531864	-94.358596	2487	2023-09-04T15:07:58.088Z
S0573	Sendero del Cangrejo	S573-IGT3	16	2.531777	-94.358746	2500	2023-09-04T16:27:05.122Z
S0573	Sendero del Cangrejo	S573-IGT4	20	2.531778	-94.358751	2500	2023-09-04T16:39:27.182Z
S0575	Iguanas	S575-IGT1	303	2.104200	-91.925089	1673	2023-09-07T23:53:47.535Z
S0575	Iguanas	S575-IGT2	301	2.104206	-91.925096	1673	2023-09-08T00:20:59.092Z
S0575	Iguanas	S575-IGT3	26	2.104173	-91.925108	1677	2023-09-08T05:16:21.760Z
S0575	Iguanas	S575-IGT4	26	2.104183	-91.925126	1677	2023-09-08T05:32:32.786Z
S0576	Iguanas	S576-IGT1	323	2.105028	-91.937803	1672	2023-09-09T09:41:21.732Z
S0576	Iguanas	S576-IGT2	326	2.105027	-91.937805	1672	2023-09-09T10:00:10.913Z
S0576	Iguanas	S576-IGT3	292	2.104833	-91.938103	1671	2023-09-09T17:51:26.037Z
S0576	Iguanas	S576-IGT4	293	2.104828	-91.938107	1671	2023-09-09T18:04:27.887Z

Geological sampling

Hydrothermal mineral and marine sediment samples were collected during ROV *SuBastian* dives in order to examine the mineralogy, geochemical composition, and rates and processes of hydrothermal mineral formation and alteration at active and inactive vent sites along the spreading center. Several basalt samples were also collected.

Table 9: Summary of marine mineral samples.

Sample Type	Planned Analyses	Quantity	Lead
Sediment, whole push cores	Computed tomography, gamma density, magnetic susceptibility, mineralogy, major, minor and trace element composition	12	Gartman
Sediment, push core subsamples	Organic carbon, total mercury, methylmercury	88	Gartman
Porewater	Temperature, pH, Fe(II)/Fe(III), nutrients, total mercury, trace metals	61	Gartman
Hydrothermal minerals	Mineralogy, major, minor and trace element composition (Gartman); S isotopes (McDermott)	56 for all analysis; 18 for sulfur isotopes	Gartman; McDermott

Push core samples

Push core samples were collected from 18 locations near active and inactive vent fields and away from hydrothermal activity (i.e., background sites). Cores sample abbreviations were PC (for push core) a number which corresponded to the number on the tube, and either T (for tall) which indicated 50 cm tubes which were returned whole to PCMSC, or S (for short) which indicated a 20 cm core with pre-drilled holes for the extraction of pore waters followed by shipboard subsampling and preservation for organic carbon, total mercury, and methylmercury. When possible, cores were collected in duplicate, with one T and one S core per location to generate complimentary datasets. Where the collection of only one core was possible, that core was returned whole. Both T and S cores were measured, photographed, and described shipboard prior to preservation or subsampling. Porewater extracted from the S cores was analyzed shipboard for pH, T and Fe(II)/(III) via ferrozine, with remaining fluids preserved via freezing at -20 or -30 C for later nutrient and trace metal analyses. After the extraction of pore waters, the core was then subsampled and frozen at -20 or -30 C for later sedimentary analysis of organic carbon and mercury. The whole core had overlying fluids removed after measurement of T and pH and was then capped and stored in a cold room for later analyses and subsampling.

Table 10: Metadata for push core samples collected with ROV *SuBastian*.

Dive	Vent Site	Sample ID	Latitude (dd)	Longitude (dd)	Water Depth (m)	Timestamp (UTC)
S0562	Iguanas	PC1T, PC1S	2.1048	-91.9376	1670	2023-08-19T16:13:44.997Z
S0563	Iguanas	PC1T	2.1045	-91.9260	1669	2023-08-20T23:28:22.808Z
S0564	Iguanas	PC1T, PC1S	2.1063	-91.9275	1691	2023-08-21T17:38:44.934Z
S0567	--	PC1T, PC1S	2.4951	-93.6994	2375	2023-08-26T13:40:36.229Z
S0570	Navidad	PC1T, PC1S	2.5290	-94.0727	2431	2023-08-30T00:32:11.927Z
S0570	Navidad	PC3S	2.5276	-94.0745	2409	2023-08-30T02:28:40.558Z
S0570	Navidad	PC4S	2.5272	-94.0692	2395	2023-08-29T06:55:56.227Z
S0571	Sendero	PC1T, PC1S	2.5494	-94.3834	2400	2023-09-01T10:01:33.036Z
S0571	Sendero	PC3T, PC3S	2.5317	-94.3586	2487	2023-09-02T14:42:11.310Z
S0571	Sendero	PC4T, PC4S	2.5274	-94.3529	2507	2023-09-01T19:56:54.496Z
S0573	Sendero	PC1S	2.5317	-94.3585	2485	2023-09-04T18:19:05.792Z
S0573	Sendero	PC3T, PC3S	2.5317	-94.3585	2487	2023-09-04T17:48:32.123Z
S0574	Iguanas	PC3T, PC3S	2.1044	-91.9256	1666	2023-09-06T05:51:51.208Z
S0574	Iguanas	PC4S	2.1044	-91.9256	1667	2023-09-06T05:10:33.412Z
S0575	Iguanas	PC3T, PC3S	2.1045	-91.9261	1669	2023-09-08T08:23:52.528Z
S0575	Iguanas	PC4S	2.1045	-91.9261	1669	2023-09-08T08:13:00.468Z
S0576	Iguanas	PC1T, PC1S	2.1186	-91.9354	1760	2023-09-10T00:27:47.197Z
S0576	Iguanas	PC3S	2.1046	-91.9362	1668	2023-09-09T22:15:57.008Z

Hydrothermal mineral samples

Active and inactive hydrothermal minerals including chimney and talus samples were collected, described shipboard, and stored frozen at -20 or -30 C for later mineralogy, geochemical, and isotopic analyses (n = 56) (**Table A4**). The active chimney samples were collected from vents where high temperature fluid was sampled using Isobaric Gas Tights. Where relevant, active chimney samples were split for sulfur isotope and microbial analyses.

Table 11: Metadata for active sulfide samples collected with ROV *SuBastian* that are targeted for S isotopes, including associated vent fluid IDs.

Dive	Vent Site	Mineral Sample ID	Paired IGT Samples	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat (dd)	Long (dd)	Timestamp
S0562	Iguanas	S562-R02	IGT1, IGT2	127.584	1656.21	2.104403	-91.936317	2023-08-19T11:29:16.965Z
S0563	Iguanas	S563-R03-B	IGT3, IGT4	329.178	1644.13	2.104943	-91.926278	2023-08-20T22:29:08.338Z
S0564	Iguanas	S564-R01-D	IGT1, IGT2	333.073	1660.44	2.103955	-91.926471	2023-08-22T02:13:11.539Z
S0564	Iguanas	S564-R03-B	IGT4	263.798	1648.55	2.104885	-91.926239	2023-08-22T07:23:53.245Z
S0565	Pinguinos	S565*	Not paired	187.427	1659.06	2.099103	-91.906413	2023-08-23T07:51:07.023Z
S0565	Pinguinos	S565-R03-B	IGT1, IGT2	77.646	1669.47	2.099438	-91.906128	2023-08-23T10:05:51.969Z
S0565	Pinguinos	S565-R06-B	IGT3, IGT4	87.396	1663.28	2.099346	-91.906136	2023-08-23T21:01:23.701Z
S0566	Pinguinos	S566-R05-B	IGT1, IGT2	136.269	1670.95	2.099292	-91.905472	2023-08-24T17:20:27.078Z
S0568	Navidad	S568-R02-B	IGT1, IGT2	119.295	2409.33	2.527699	-94.075119	2023-08-28T01:45:40.168Z
S0568	Navidad	S568-R05-B	Not paired	350.898	2409.27	2.527229	-94.075455	2023-08-28T05:25:34.696Z
S0568	Navidad	S568-R07-B	IGT3, IGT4	350.865	2409.19	2.527231	-94.075461	2023-08-28T05:57:24.649Z
S0570	Navidad	S570-R05-B	IGT1, IGT2	144.08	2391.21	2.527287	-94.076095	2023-08-29T15:08:59.579Z
S0571	Sendero del Cangrejo	S571-R08-C	IGT1, IGT2	92.087	2486.36	2.531721	-94.358657	2023-09-02T14:55:19.484Z
S0572	Sendero del Cangrejo	S572-R01-B	IGT1, IGT2	65.341	2477.5	2.531934	-94.35907	2023-09-03T17:08:22.761Z

Dive	Vent Site	Mineral Sample ID	Paired IGT Samples	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat (dd)	Long (dd)	Timestamp
S0573	Sendero del Cangrejo	S573-R01-B	IGT1, IGT2	323.355	2467.98	2.531907	-94.358564	2023-09-04T10:12:35.140Z
S0573	Sendero del Cangrejo	S573-R03-B	IGT1, IGT2	295.417	2488.75	2.531672	-94.358556	2023-09-04T18:58:50.392Z
S0575	Iguanas	S575-R01-B	IGT1, IGT2	323.124	1666.06	2.104189	-91.925084	2023-09-08T00:37:26.271Z
S0575	Iguanas	S576-R01-B	IGT1, IGT2	59.002	1673.64	2.105024	-91.937802	2023-09-09T10:56:44.735Z

Distributed Temperature Sensing

Distributed temperature sensing (DTS) measures temperature synoptically along an optical fiber at discrete measurement sections 0.25m in length. An in situ DTS observatory consisting of a DTS, battery, two fiber reels containing 420m and 560m of ruggedized sensing fiber, and a SeaBird 39+ TD probe was deployed at the Iguanas vent field. On dive S564, *SuBastian* retrieved the deployed lander and placed it at the survey site (2.106242oN, -91.926751oE, depth 1686.12m) at 13:01 UTC on 08/22/2023. Grabbing a line attached to the unterminated end of the fiber, *SuBastian* then proceeded to unspool 165m of fiber onto the seafloor at a bearing of 075. On the return to the lander, ROV *SuBastian* performed a visual survey of the fiber. Two Lowell Instruments Tilt Current Meters (TCM), each with two iButtons attached to their base and one independent iButton thermistor were deployed along this fiber at points of interest. This process was then repeated on the second fiber. 120m of this fiber were unspooled onto the seafloor at a bearing of 015. One TCM payload and one independent iButton were deployed along this second fiber. The DTS deployment process was completed at 16:06 UTC. The DTS observatory and auxiliary sensors were left ~15 days until the vessel returned to station on dive S574 (09/06/2023). All sensors were recovered and secured to the lander. After all sensors were retrieved, ROV *SuBastian* flew over the fiber at an altitude of 5m to perform a visual survey and map the fiber's surroundings using the MAPR. Both fibers were then spooled onto their respective reels. The lander was then left on the seafloor until its weights were manually released on dive S575 (09/07/2023). Preliminary results from this deployment show correlation between temperature variability across the vent field ocean and earth tides.

Figure 13: DTS observatory lander during fiber deployment on S564.

Table 12: Summary of data set collected in association with the DTS project.

Sensor	Measurement Parameter	Location Name	Lat	Lon	Depth (m)	Start Time	End Time	Duration	Sampling Rate
Lander	N/A	Lander	2.10399	- 91.926621	1676	08/22 13:28	09/07 23:09	16d 9h 41m	N/A
DTS Fiber 1	Temperature	Lander to Fiber 1 End	2.104352	- 91.925252	1674	08/22 13:55	08/29 17:52	7d 1h 57m	120s
DTS Fiber 2	Temperature	Lander to Fiber 2 End	2.105105	- 91.926342	1664	08/22 15:28	08/29 17:52	7d 0h 24m	120s
SBE 39+ TD Probe	Temperature, Pressure	Lander	2.10399	- 91.926621	1676	08/22 13:28	09/06 00:44	14d 11h 16m	0.5s
TCM 1	Current, Temperature	TCM 1	2.103959	- 91.926532	1676	08/22 14:30	09/06 01:40	14d 11h 10m	60s
TCM 2	Current, Temperature	TCM 2	2.104088	- 91.926044	1676	08/22 14:51	09/06 01:22	14d 10h 31m	60s
TCM 3	Current, Temperature	TCM 3	2.105000	- 91.926397	1661	08/22 16:06	09/06 02:28	14d 10h 22m	60s
iButton 1	Temperature	Lander	2.10399	- 91.926621	1676	08/22 13:28	09/06 00:44	14d 11h 16m	360s
iButton 2	Temperature	TCM 1	2.103959	- 91.926532	1676	08/22 14:30	09/06 01:40	14d 11h 10m	180s
iButton 3	Temperature	TCM 1	2.103959	- 91.926532	1676	08/22 14:30	09/06 01:40	14d 11h 10m	360s
iButton 4	Temperature	TCM 2	2.104088	- 91.926044	1676	08/22 14:51	09/06 01:22	14d 10h 31m	180s
iButton 5	Temperature	TCM 2	2.104088	- 91.926044	1676	08/22 14:51	09/06 01:22	14d 10h 31m	360s

Sensor	Measurement Parameter	Location Name	Lat	Lon	Depth (m)	Start Time	End Time	Duration	Sampling Rate
iButton 6	Temperature	TCM 3	2.105000	-91.926397	1661	08/22 16:06	09/06 02:28	14d 10h 22m	180s
iButton 7	Temperature	TCM 3	2.105000	-91.926397	1661	08/22 16:06	09/06 02:28	14d 10h 22m	360s
iButton 8	Temperature	iButton 1	2.103968	-91.92652	1676	08/22 14:46	09/06 2:01	14d 11h 15m	360s
iButton 9	Temperature	iButton 2	2.104188	-91.92655	1675	08/22 15:56	09/06 02:39	14d 10h 43m	360s

CTD Niskin Water Samples

Background seawater was collected from CTD_001 and used to backfill open space in the IGTs prior to their deployment. This seawater was also collected as a scientific sample and used to constrain ambient deep-water chemistry, as a contrast to the local vent chemistry.

CTD Niskin water was also sampled for microorganisms by the Anantharaman lab. After the CTD was returned to deck, 40-80L of seawater from the Niskins was filtered onto filters with a pore size of 0.03 μm using a custom-built filtration device. The water was obtained by connecting sterilized tubing directly to the Niskin spouts and using a peristaltic pump to pull the water through the filtration device. Following filtration, the filters were preserved in a solution of RNAlater, kept at 4°C overnight, and then stored at -80°C to preserve nucleic acids for later processing. These filters are meant to be processed in a lab to extract DNA and RNA to understand microbial diversity and metabolisms, but are currently still at the Darwin Marine Station due to permit issues.

Table 13: Metadata for microbial samples taken from CTD Niskins.

CTD ID	Date_Time_UTC	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon	Sample Type	Sample ID	Niskins	Volume filtered (L)
CTD_001	08/18/2023_15:32:42	1691	1.409459	-91.458355	Background water	FKt230812-CTD1-A	4-9, 24	70L
CTD_002	08/24/2023_05:07:18	1615	2.099095	-91.905108	Unlikely plume	FKt230812-CTD2-A	1-8	80L
CTD_004	08/30/23_23:19:19	2381	2.539228	-94.350376	Likely plume	FKt230812-CTD4- A	13-16	40L
CTD_004	08/30/23_22:26:14	2381	2.539814	-94.357712	Background, near plume	FKt230812-CTD4-B	9-12	40L
CTD_005	09/04/23_03:56:18	2464	2.531775	-94.358764	Likely plume	FKt230812-CTD5-A	2-7	60L
CTD_006	09/08/23_00:37:48	1615	2.104716	-91.925195	Likely plume	FKt230812-CTD6-A	1-8	80L
CTD_006	09/08/23_00:51:11	1610	2.104506	-91.925279	Likely plume	FKt230812-CTD6-B	17-23	80L

2.2.2 New Discoveries

The science team discovered thriving cold-water coral reefs with a high biodiversity of associated organisms in a marine protected area with little deep-sea scientific information. Two major currents, the cold South Equatorial Current and the warmer Panama Current, flow around them while the Pacific Equatorial Undercurrent interacts directly with the islands. In addition to oceanographic patterns, the Galápagos also provides a valuable laboratory for studying island geology. The islands are built on pedestals of stacked lava flows — some of which are exposed, offering a stratified geological history of the archipelago. The oceanographic complexity of the region plays an essential role in understanding past and future climatic conditions.

2.3 Data

Datasets acquired during this expedition and those derived from the analysis of collected data and samples as of this report's publication date.

Data Type	Curator	Completed
Vessel underway data	Rolling Deck to Repository	Yes
ADCP data	University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System	Yes
Processed multibeam sonar	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Yes
ROV <i>SuBastian</i> Sensor Data	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Yes
ROV Image Data	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Yes
ROV Event Log Data	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Yes
Genetic and genomic data		No
Physico-chemical properties		No
Mineralogical data		No

2.4 Publications

Banks, S., Alonso, D., Vides, M., Yepes, V., Cortes, J., Naranjo-Elizondo, B., et al. (2025). Unveiling Hidden Dimensions of the Eastern Tropical Pacific Marine Conservation Corridor. *Journal of Ocean Technology*, 20 (2),

3. Appendix

3.1 Science Party Information

Scientist	Institution
Roxanne Beinart	University of Rhode Island
Jill McDermott	Lehigh University
Stuart Banks	Charles Darwin Foundation
Johann Becker	University of Rhode Island
Esmira Bibaj	Lehigh University
Katlin Bowman Adamczyk	US Geological Survey
Corinna Breusing	University of Rhode Island
Hayley Drennon	Columbia University
Jaycee Favela	US Geological Survey
Vicki Ferrini	Columbia University
Amy Gartman	US Geological Survey

Scientist	Institution
Peter Girguis	Harvard University
Rachel Harris	Harvard University
Michelle Hauer	University of Rhode Island
Santiago Herrera	Lehigh University
Katie Klier	University of Wisconsin–Madison
Marguerite Langwig	University of Wisconsin–Madison
Dennisse Maldonado	Instituto Oceanográfico y Antártico de la Armada (INOCAR)
Nicole Pittoors	Lehigh University
Jessica Rodgers	Lehigh University
Jada Siverand	Lehigh University
Andrea Unzeueta Martinez	Harvard University
Ricardo Visaira Coronel	Galapagos National Park
Jacob Winnikoff	Harvard University
Philip Yang	University of Rhode Island

3.2 Conferences/Presentations/Posters

Harris, R.L. "Act locally, [re]think globally: A microbial perspective of habitability and ecosystem-scale processes and how we might be underestimating the extent of habitable refugia in astrobiological targets". *Invited Talk*. American Geophysical Union Fall Meeting, San Francisco, CA. 2023.

Girguis, P.R. *Oral Presentation*. United Nations Ocean Conference 3, Paris, France (virtual). 2023.

Girguis, P.R. *Oral Presentation*. Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, MD. 2023.

Girguis, P.R. *Oral Presentation*. University of Connecticut, Storrs, MA (virtual). 2023.

Harris, R.L. "Prolific methane oxidizing capacity by hydrothermal vent microbes: An overlooked sink in the marine methane budget". *Invited Talk*. Biology and Paleo Environment Division Seminar Series, Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory, Columbia University, Palisades, NY. 2023.

Harris, R.L., and Girguis, P.R. "Redox biosignatures at metalliferous mid ocean ridge systems". *Oral Presentation*. Exploring Ocean Worlds annual meeting, Tempe, AZ. 2023.

Winnikoff, J.R., Harris, R.L., and Girguis, P.R. "Biophysical and Energetic Demands of Pressure and Temperature". *Poster*. AbSciCon, Providence, RI. 2024.

Winnikoff, J.R. "Homeocurvature and homeoviscosity: unifying principles of membrane adaptation". *Keynote presentation*. High Pressure Bioscience and Biotechnology, Lyon, France. 2024.

Bibaj, E., Siverand, J.M., Rodgers, J.C., Beinart, R., McDermott, J.M. "Hydrothermal Activity Along the Western Galápagos Spreading Center: Sampling Black Smokers 46 Years After the Discovery of Seafloor Hydrothermal Systems". *Oral Presentation*. American Geophysical Union Fall Meeting, Washington, DC. 2024.

Becker, J., Beinart, R., Girguis, P.R., Soule, S., Phillips, B.T. "High spatiotemporal observations of temperature variability at hydrothermal vent fields using fiber optic distributed sensing". *iPoster/e-Lightning talk*. ASLO Ocean Sciences Meeting, New Orleans, LA. 2024.

Bibaj, E., Tanaka, R., Herrera, S., Rodgers, J., Siverand, J., McDermott, J.M. "Triple Oxygen Isotope Signatures of Hydrothermal Systems: Insights from the East Pacific Rise, Western Galápagos Spreading Rift, and the American Samoa Intraplate Volcano". *Poster*. American Geophysical Union Fall Meeting, New Orleans, LA. 2025.

Unzueta-Martínez, A. "The Microbial Physiology Within: Uncovering the Layers of Bivalve Biomineralization". *Invited seminar*. Department of Biological Sciences Colloquium, University of Massachusetts Lowell, Lowell, MA. 2025.

Winnikoff, J.R. "Unifying principles of membrane adaptation to pressure-temperature niches in the ocean". *Departmental seminar*. UConn Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, Storrs, CT. 2025.

Winnikoff, J.R. "Unifying principles of membrane adaptation to pressure-temperature niches in the ocean". *Departmental seminar*. UConn Marine Sciences, Avery Point, CT. 2025.

Winnikoff, J.R. "Structural adaptation of lipids to support dynamic membrane function and life at extremes". *Departmental seminar*. UConn Molecular and Cellular Biology, Storrs, CT. 2025.

Harris, R.L. "Prolific methane oxidizing capacity by hydrothermal vent microbes: An overlooked sink in the marine methane budget". Guest Lecturer. CAS EE 443 – Terrestrial Biogeochemistry, Boston University, College of Arts and Sciences, Dept. of Earth and Environment, Boston, MA. 2024.

3.3 Cruise Records

- [Cruise log](#).
- [ROV Dive Playlist](#).

3.4 Media

"Five Questions with Peter R. Girguis" by Olivia Farrar. 2025. Harvard Magazine.

<https://www.harvardmagazine.com/five-questions/harvard-professor-peter-girguis-marine-biology>

3.5 Community Outreach

Bowman Adamczyk, K. "Discovery of new deep-sea hydrothermal vents in the western Galapagos Spreading Center". *Public talk*. The Explorers Club Next Generation Speaker Series, Asia Society, New York, NY. 2025.

Bowman Adamczyk, K. "Sendero del Cangrejo". *Lightning talk*. California Explorers Club and National Geographic Learning collaborative outreach event, Center for Performing Arts, Carmel, CA. 2025.

3.6 Detailed Sample Metadata

Table A1: Metadata for metazoan collections. ROV locations were Biobox (BB), Suction Sampler (SS), or Coral Quiver (CQ).

Dive	Date_Time_UTC	Vent field	Locality	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon	Collection_ID	ROV location	Primary Taxon
S0562	2023-08-19T05:09:09.882Z	Iguanas	Near Waypoint 3	193.491	1662	2.104853	-91.938065	SS1	SS1	Polychaetes
S0562	2023-08-19T09:54:28.930Z	Iguanas	Diffuse flow near mussel cluster	201.44	1663	2.104837	-91.938083	Animal 1	BB1	Bathymodiolus
S0562	2023-08-19T10:44:59.195Z	Iguanas	Above small chimney with tmax 207; worm temp 3.5C	102.849	1667	2.104485	-91.936579	Animal 2	BB1	Tevnia
S0562	2023-08-19T19:47:11.697Z	Iguanas	Black smoker	302.141	1648	2.104336	-91.93632	SS2	SS2	Polychaetes
S0562	2023-08-19T20:38:10.202Z	Iguanas	Near Black Smoker 3, on inactive chimney	158.203	1672	2.105085	-91.937824	Animal 3	CQ6	Anemone
S0563	2023-08-20T12:11:40.556Z	Iguanas	Diffuse flow at Biosample Site 1	278.657	1669	2.103953	-91.926404	SS1	SS1	Polychaetes, shrimp

Dive	Date_Time_UTC	Vent field	Locality	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon	Collection_ID	ROV location	Primary Taxon
			- mussels and clams							
S0563	2023-08-20T12:25:49.549Z	Iguanas	Diffuse flow at Biosample Site 1 - mussels and clams	278.465	1669	2.103955	-91.926405	Animal 1	BB1	Bathymodiolus, Turneroconcha
S0564	2023-08-22T01:32:28.366Z	Iguanas	Chimlet 1	218.535	1668	2.10402	-91.926499	SS1	SS1	Polychaetes
S0564	2023-08-22T08:57:47.698Z	Iguanas	Clams 5	97.306	1668	2.104074	-91.926546	Animal 1	BB2	Bathymodiolus
S0564	2023-08-22T09:06:32.068Z	Iguanas	Clams 5	97.306	1669	2.104074	-91.926546	Animal 2	BB2	Turneroconcha
S0565	2023-08-23T20:39:08.416Z	Pinguinos	Active 2	151.743	1663	2.09934	-91.906133	Animal 1	BB2	Bathymodiolus
S0565	2023-08-23T21:01:23.701Z	Pinguinos	Active 3	153.94	1664	2.099346	-91.906136	Animal 2	BB2	Alvinella
S0565	2023-08-23T23:46:42.551Z	Pinguinos	Midwater; ascent	330.101	1333	2.102028	-91.905013	Animal 3	SS1	Vampyroctena
S0566	2023-08-24T09:51:11.404Z	Pinguinos	Near potential Chimney M	37.634	1679	2.100743	-91.905185	SS1	SS1	Dandelion siphonophore

Dive	Date_Time_UTC	Vent field	Locality	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon	Collection_ID	ROV location	Primary Taxon
S0566	2023-08-24T18:11:04.784Z	Pinguinos		145.475	1644	2.098911	-91.906141	SS2	SS2	Ctenophore
S0566	2023-08-24T21:25:39.434Z	Pinguinos	Chimney F	52.114	1663	2.09934	-91.905407	Animal 1	BB2	Tevnia
S0566	2023-08-24T21:25:39.434Z	Pinguinos	Chimney F	52.114	1663	2.09934	-91.905407	Animal 2	BB3	Limpets
S0567	2023-08-26T11:08:21.151Z	DSL2a	Benthic. Near-chimney SuPR site, possibly?	44.627	2392	2.492511	-93.697378	SS1	SS1	Ctenophore
S0568	2023-08-27T14:34:55.596Z	Navidad		273.373	1087	2.526564	-94.075534	SS1	SS1	Ctenophore
S0568	2023-08-27T14:38:19.715Z	Navidad		274.68	1118	2.526665	-94.075374	SS2	SS2	Ctenophore
S0568	2023-08-27T21:25:03.803Z	Navidad	Mussels 1	270.406	2404	2.527449	-94.075516	Animal 1	BB1	Bathymodiolus
S0568	2023-08-28T10:23:31.765Z	Navidad		282.766	2400	2.527133	-94.074149	Animal 2	CQ9	Cnidarian
S0570	2023-08-29T09:50:34.152Z	Navidad	Chimney 4	140.416	2410	2.527629	-94.074612	Animal 1 (R03)	BB1	Spaghetti worms
S0570	2023-08-29T20:26:37.027Z	Navidad	Mussels 1	305.662	2407	2.527301	-94.075479	Animal 2	BB2	Bathymodiolus

Dive	Date_Time_UTC	Vent field	Locality	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon	Collection_ID	ROV location	Primary Taxon
S0570	2023-08-29T21:11:02.112Z	Navidad	Mussels 1	297.999	2407	2.527303	-94.075479	Animal 3	CQ5	Bathymodiolus
S0570	2023-08-30T01:03:22.091Z	Navidad	On our way to Inactive 3 coming from background push cores	209.114	2406	2.528105	-94.073774	Animal 4	CQ10	Coral
S0570	2023-08-30T13:31:17.147Z	Navidad		210.405	1159	2.52774	-94.075491	SS1	SS2	Beroe
S0570	2023-08-30T13:48:12.720Z	Navidad		198.616	981	2.5282	-94.075351	SS2	SS3	Ctenophore
S0570	2023-08-30T14:17:20.230Z	Navidad		207.46	519	2.528133	-94.074686	SS3	SS4	Ctenophore
S0570	2023-08-30T14:27:34.297Z	Navidad		273.296	354	2.528368	-94.07484	SS4	SS5	Ctenophore
S0570	2023-08-30T14:29:20.194Z	Navidad		275.273	309	2.528365	-94.074865	SS5	SS6	Ctenophore
S0571	2023-09-02T08:57:06.829Z	Sendero del Cangrejo (DSL2b)	Chimney 2	97.844	2478	2.531942	-94.359067	Animal 1		Riftia

Dive	Date_Time_UTC	Vent field	Locality	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon	Collection_ID	ROV location	Primary Taxon
S0571	2023-09-02T10:51:58.244Z	Sendero del Cangrejo (DSL2b)	Chimlet 1	2.703	2478	2.531862	-94.358587	Animal 2		Bathymodiolus
S0571	2023-09-02T21:27:06.435Z	Sendero del Cangrejo (DSL2b)	Waypoint 17	285.98	2488	2.530464	-94.356928	Animal 3		Coral
S0571	2023-09-02T21:40:52.148Z	Sendero del Cangrejo (DSL2b)	Near Waypoint 17	295.334	2488	2.530449	-94.356939	Animal 4		Barnacle
S0572	2023-09-03T12:34:04.496Z	Sendero del Cangrejo (DSL2b)	NA	3.911	2484	2.532389	-94.35442	CQ2A	CQ2	Benthic ctenophore
S0572	2023-09-03T13:07:59.270Z	Sendero del Cangrejo (DSL2b)	NA	8.015	2480	2.536054	-94.354077	CQ2B	CQ2	Benthic ctenophore
S0572	2023-09-03T21:09:48.196Z	Sendero del Cangrejo (DSL2b)	NA	215.359	2474	2.531838	-94.357955	SS8	SS8	Dandelion siphonophore

Dive	Date_Time_UTC	Vent field	Locality	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon	Collection_ID	ROV location	Primary Taxon
S0572	2023-09-03T22:55:03.561Z	Sendero del Cangrejo (DSL2b)	Chimlet 1	102.057	2468	2.531947	-94.358627	Animal 1		Riftia
S0573	2023-09-04T12:25:10.019Z	Sendero del Cangrejo (DSL2b)	Below Chimlet 1 on Dave/Ben's Wall marker	1.796	2472	2.531869	-94.358574	Animal 1		Riftia
S0573	2023-09-04T20:12:21.245Z	Sendero del Cangrejo (DSL2b)	Background - check again	345.086	2490	2.531789	-94.358987	Animal 2		Coral
S0574	2023-09-05T23:52:35.688Z	Iguanas	Midwater, descent	156.3	617	2.104153	-91.92711	SS1	SS1	Ctenophore
S0575	2023-09-07T21:38:48.293Z	Iguanas	Midwater, descent	228.752	324	2.102972	-91.927165	Animal 1	SS1	Ctenophore
S0575	2023-09-08T04:01:09.760Z	Iguanas	Base of Smoker 6/ Mussels 2	4.29	1670	2.104177	-91.925112	Animal 2	BB1	Bathymodiolus
S0575	2023-09-08T06:50:40.711Z	Iguanas	Mussels 3	135.786	1666	2.104461	-91.925654	Animal 3	BB2	Bathymodiolus
S0575	2023-09-08T11:39:57.134Z	Iguanas	Edge of Mussel bed	269.973	1668	2.104014	-91.926362	Animal 4	SS2	

Dive	Date_Time_UTC	Vent field	Locality	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon	Collection_ID	ROV location	Primary Taxon
S0575	2023-09-08T12:50:42.667Z	Iguanas	North of Chimlet 1, 30 m from SuPR2	184.279	1669	2.104431	-91.926484	Animal 5	SS3	
S0575	2023-09-08T13:57:25.938Z	Iguanas	Clams 6	186.658	1670	2.103895	-91.926457	Animal 6	BB2	Turneroconcha
S0575	2023-09-08T21:56:41.681Z	Iguanas	Background	211.135	1669	2.10408	-91.927578	Animal 7	CQ8	Octocoralia
S0576	2023-09-10T01:55:53.299Z	Iguanas	Background	5.905	1707	2.115168	-91.935672	Animal 1	BB2	Octocoralia

Table A2: Metadata for Niskin eDNA filter samples taken above chemosynthetic macrofaunal communities.

Dive	Site	Locality	Alt (m from seafloor)	HDG	Depth	Lat	Lon	Collection ID	Filter Type	Volume (L)	Sample ID
S0562	Iguanas	diffuse flow near mussel cluster	3.25	1663	1663	2.1048	-91.9381	562_Niskin_1	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.5	SH23502
S0562	Iguanas	diffuse flow near mussel cluster	3.25	1663	1663	2.1048	-91.9381	562_Niskin_2	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.8	SH23503
S0562	Iguanas	diffuse flow near mussel cluster	3.23	1663	1663	2.1048	-91.9381	562_Niskin_3	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.8	SH23504
S0563	Iguanas	biosample site1,diffuse flow mussels	0.71	278.6	1669	2.104	-91.9264	563_Niskin_1	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.5	SH23505

Dive	Site	Locality	Alt (m from sealloor)	HDG	Depth	Lat	Lon	Collection ID	Filter Type	Volume (L)	Sample ID
S0563	Iguanas	biosample site1,diffuse flow mussels	0.71	278.6	1669	2.104	-91.9264	563_Niskin_2	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.9	SH23506
S0563	Iguanas	biosample site1,diffuse flow mussels	0.71	278.6	1669	2.104	-91.9264	563_Niskin_3	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.6	SH23507
S0564	Iguanas	chimlet1	0.69	250.3	1669	2.104	-91.9264	564_Niskin_1	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	na	na
S0564	Iguanas	chimlet1	0.69	251.6	1669	2.104	-91.9264	564_Niskin_2	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.5	SH23508
S0564	Iguanas	chimlet1	0.68	251.4	1669	2.104	-91.9264	564_Niskin_3	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.6	SH23509
S0565	Pinguin os	active2	3.46	152.2	1663	2.0994	-91.9061	565_Niskin_1	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.2	SH23510
S0565	Pinguin os	active2	2.34	152.2	1663	2.0994	-91.9061	565_Niskin_2	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.8	SH23511
S0565	Pinguin os	active2	2.34	152.2	1663	2.0994	-91.9061	565_Niskin_3	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.1	SH23512
S0566	Pinguin os	Waypoint F	7.72	54.21	1664	2.0993	-91.9054	566_Niskin_1	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.5	SH23513
S0566	Pinguin os	Waypoint F	7.75	54	1664	2.0993	-91.9054	566_Niskin_2	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.7	SH23514
S0566	Pinguin os	Waypoint F	7.66	53.99	1664	2.0993	-91.9054	566_Niskin_3	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.8	SH23515

Dive	Site	Locality	Alt (m from sealloor)	HDG	Depth	Lat	Lon	Collection ID	Filter Type	Volume (L)	Sample ID
S0568	Navidad	mussel1	1.43	270.4	2404	2.5274	-94.0755	568_Niskin_2	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.6	SH23519
S0568	Navidad	mussel2	1.49	270.4	2404	2.5275	-94.0755	568_Niskin_3	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.3	SH23520
S0568	Navidad	chimney7	3.69	323.3	2405	2.5276	-94.0752	568_Niskin_5	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	2.2	SH23521
S0568	Navidad	chimney7	3.68	322.9	2405	2.5276	-94.0752	568_Niskin_6	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	2.1	SH23522
S0570	Navidad	mussel1	1.8	306.1	2407	2.5273	-94.0755	570_Niskin_1	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.1	SH23523
S0570	Navidad	mussel1	1.81	306.1	2407	2.5273	-94.0755	570_Niskin_2	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.7	SH23524
S0570	Navidad	mussel1	1.85	306.1	2407	2.5273	-94.0755	570_Niskin_3	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.8	SH23525
S0571	DSL-2B	chimney2, near Riftia	2.59	289	2476	2.5319	-94.359	571_Niskin_1	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.3	SH23526
S0571	DSL-2B	chimney2, near Riftia	3.07	289.4	2476	2.5319	-94.359	571_Niskin_2	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.6	SH23527
S0571	DSL-2B	chimney2, near Riftia	3.09	289.4	2476	2.5319	-94.359	571_Niskin_3	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	5.8	SH23528

Dive	Site	Locality	Alt (m from seafloor)	HDG	Depth	Lat	Lon	Collection ID	Filter Type	Volume (L)	Sample ID
S0572	DSL-2B	over riftia that will be sampled to the east of chymney 1	1.43	277.9	2486	2.5319	-94.3586	572_Niskin_1	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.1	SH23529
S0572	DSL-2B	over riftia that will be sampled to the east of chymney 1	1.43	277.9	2486	2.5319	-94.3586	572_Niskin_2	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.6	SH23530
S0572	DSL-2B	over riftia that will be sampled to the east of chymney 1	1.43	277.9	2486	2.5319	-94.3586	572_Niskin_3	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.4	SH23531
S0575	Iguanas	smoker6	0.77	359.7	1670	2.1042	-91.9251	575_Niskin_1	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.4	SH23535
S0575	Iguanas	smoker6	0	359.7	1670	2.1042	-91.9251	575_Niskin_2	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.7	SH23536
S0575	Iguanas	smoker6	0.78	359.7	1670	2.1042	-91.9251	575_Niskin_3	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.7	SH23537
S0576	Iguanas	smoker1	15.5	185.1	1658	2.1049	-91.9381	576_Niskin_1	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.5	SH23538
S0576	Iguanas	smoker2	12.4	185.5	1660	2.1048	-91.9381	576_Niskin_2	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.7	SH23539
S0576	Iguanas	smoker3	11.7	187.8	1660	2.1048	-91.9381	576_Niskin_3	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.7	SH23540
BLANK	milliQ	blank	na	na	na	na	na	na	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	6.4	SH23532
BLANK	milliQ	blank	na	na	na	na	na	na	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot-gravity	5.6	SH23533

Dive	Site	Locality	Alt (m from sealfoor)	HDG	Depth	Lat	Lon	Collection ID	Filter Type	Volume (L)	Sample ID
BLAN K	milliQ	blank	na	na	na	na	na	na	Sterlitech, 47mm, 5um, smithroot- gravity	6	SH23534

Table A3: Metadata for SUPR samples.

Dive #	SuPR ID	Filter #	<i>In situ</i> RNALater?	Vent Field	Timestamp	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon
S562	S562_SuPR_1_Regular	1	N	Iguanas	2023-08-19T07:23:33.221Z	232.888 m	1666.16	2.104834	-91.938063
S562	S562_SuPR_2_isRNALater	2	Y	Iguanas	2023-08-19T07:39:24.301Z	232.564 m	1666.24	2.104836	-91.938062
S562	S562_SuPR_3_Regular	3	N	Iguanas	2023-08-19T08:08:52.465Z	220.787 m	1653.24	2.104873	-91.938026
S562	S562_SuPR_4_isRNALater	4	Y	Iguanas	2023-08-19T08:28:36.748Z	222.621 m	1653.33	2.104864	-91.938025
S562	S562_SuPR_5_Regular	5	N	Iguanas	2023-08-19T09:00:10.480Z	201.324 m	1663.01	2.104838	-91.93809
S562	S562_SuPR_6_isRNALater	6	Y	Iguanas	2023-08-19T09:16:16.422Z	201.473 m	1663.03	2.104828	-91.93809
S562	S562_SuPR_8_Regular	8	N	Iguanas	2023-08-19T17:13:57.759Z	235.569 m	1669.76	2.103236	-91.936536
S562	S562_SuPR_9_Regular	9	N	Iguanas	2023-08-19T21:09:10.962Z	194.299 m	1670.84	2.104936	-91.938098
S562	S562_SuPR_10_Regular	10	N	Iguanas	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
S563	S563_SuPR_1_Regular	1	N	Iguanas	2023-08-20T11:04:27.665Z	277.465 m	1669.45	2.103923	-91.926374
S563	S563_SuPR_2_isRNALater	2	Y	Iguanas	2023-08-20T11:16:47.199Z	277.487 m	1669.43	2.103941	-91.926389
S563	S563_SuPR_3_Regular	3	N	Iguanas	2023-08-20T17:23:58.859Z	76.245 m	1667.58	2.103942	-91.926559
S563	S563_SuPR_4_isRNALater	4	Y	Iguanas	2023-08-20T17:39:47.561Z	76.289 m	1667.61	2.104006	-91.926552
S563	S563_SuPR_5_Regular	5	N	Iguanas	2023-08-20T18:55:18.575Z	266.55 m	1617.94	2.104976	-91.926134
S563	S563_SuPR_6_isRNALater	6	Y	Iguanas	2023-08-20T19:11:24.106Z	256.234 m	1615.51	2.105004	-91.926131
S563	S563_SuPR_7_Regular	7	N	Iguanas	2023-08-20T20:16:45.990Z	258.426 m	1638.82	2.10514	-91.92623

Dive #	SuPR ID	Filter #	<i>In situ</i> RNALater?	Vent Field	Timestamp	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon
S563	S563_SuPR_8_isRNALater	8	Y	Iguanas	2023-08-20T20:31:34.874Z	239.288 m	1638.87	2.105148	-91.926231
S563	S563_SuPR_9_Regular	9	N	Iguanas	2023-08-21T00:55:52.255Z	10.459 m	1671.14	2.106136	-91.924938
S563	S563_SuPR_10_isRNALater	10	Y	Iguanas	2023-08-21T01:10:11.302Z	272.027 m	1672.53	2.105876	-91.925106
S563	S563_SuPR_11_Regular	11	N	Iguanas	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
S563	S563_SuPR_12_isRNALater	12	Y	Iguanas	2023-08-21T01:31:59.632Z	296.208 m	1661.16	2.10524	-91.925074
S564	S564_SuPR_1_Regular	1	N	Iguanas	2023-08-21T17:18:02.007Z	271.176 m	1688.28 (transect)	2.10626 (transect)	-91.926949 (transect)
S564	S564_SuPR_2_isRNALater	2	Y	Iguanas	2023-08-21T22:42:19.618Z	166.234 m	1667.83	2.104018	-91.92651
S564	S564_SuPR_3_Regular	3	N	Iguanas	2023-08-22T00:32:10.967Z	188.663 m	1668.34	2.104015	-91.92651
S564	S564_SuPR_4_Regular	4	N	Iguanas	2023-08-22T04:34:48.037Z	47.335 m	1664.77	2.104335	-91.925533
S564	S564_SuPR_5_Regular	5	N	Iguanas	2023-08-22T04:55:11.384Z	44.297 m	1646.2	2.104332	-91.925508
S564	S564_SuPR_6_Regular	6	N	Iguanas	2023-08-22T08:13:54.470Z	96.861 m	1668.28	2.104084	-91.926546
S564	S564_SuPR_7_Regular	7	N	Iguanas	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
S564	S564_SuPR_8_Regular	8	N	Iguanas	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
S565	S565_SuPR_2_Regular	2	N	Pinguinos	2023-08-23T12:05:20.379Z	69.049 m	1668.65	2.099434	-91.906144
S565	S565_SuPR_3_Regular	3	N	Pinguinos	2023-08-23T12:25:42.780Z	63.704 m	1648.91	2.099447	-91.906122
S565	S565_SuPR_4_Regular	4	N	Pinguinos	2023-08-23T12:47:55.494Z	64.204 m	1669.07	2.099517	-91.906192
S565	S565_SuPR_5_Regular	5	N	Pinguinos	2023-08-23T19:26:36.146Z	150.683 m	1663.11	2.099355	-91.906151

Dive #	SuPR ID	Filter #	<i>In situ</i> RNALater?	Vent Field	Timestamp	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon
S565	S565_SuPR_6_Regular	6	N	Pinguinos	2023-08-23T22:10:47.567Z	138.439 m	1663.77	2.099351	-91.906146
S565	S565_SuPR_7_Regular	7	N	Pinguinos	2023-08-23T22:56:26.287Z	342.307 m	1679.75	2.101066	-91.905759
S566	S566_SuPR_1_isRNALater	1	Y	Pinguinos	2023-08-24T10:56:48.052Z	75.13 m	1669.33	2.099421	-91.906137
S566	S566_SuPR_2_isRNALater	2	Y	Pinguinos	2023-08-24T11:27:24.273Z	74.191 m	1669.64	2.09942	-91.906131
S566	S566_SuPR_3_isRNALater	3	Y	Pinguinos	2023-08-24T12:04:04.437Z	5.85 m	1666.06	2.09953	-91.906241
S568	S568_SuPR_1_Regular	1	N	Navidad	2023-08-27T20:11:19.150Z	270.972 m	2404.05	2.527446	-94.075528
S568	S568_SuPR_2_Regular	2	N	Navidad	2023-08-28T02:56:56.832Z	343.394 m	2408.84	2.527225	-94.075453
S568	S568_SuPR_3_Regular	3	N	Navidad	2023-08-28T03:16:22.510Z	328.447 m	2407.46	2.527218	-94.075437
S568	S568_SuPR_4_Regular	4	N	Navidad	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
S568	S568_SuPR_5_Regular	5	N	Navidad	2023-08-28T06:51:14.145Z	346.915 m	2409.53	2.527161	-94.07544
S568	S568_SuPR_6_Regular	6	N	Navidad	2023-08-28T07:29:19.689Z	245.709 m	2406.81	2.527295	-94.07547
S568	S568_SuPR_7_Regular.DIED	7	N	Navidad	2023-08-28T10:42:08.434Z	129.172 m	2367.66	2.526298	-94.073467
S568	S568_SuPR_7_Regular.redo	7	N	Navidad	2023-08-28T10:57:04.721Z	128.073 m	2368.47	2.5263	-94.073453
S570	S570_SuPR_1_Regular	1	N	Navidad	2023-08-29T06:24:35.621Z	179.187	2393.95	2.527595	-94.069427
S570	S570_SuPR_2_Regular	2	N	Navidad	2023-08-29T11:54:27.075Z	148.31	2391.22	2.527274	-94.076106
S570	S570_SuPR_3_Regular	3	N	Navidad	2023-08-29T12:14:43.711Z	160.192	2386.6	2.527276	-94.076096

Dive #	SuPR ID	Filter #	<i>In situ</i> RNAlater?	Vent Field	Timestamp	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon
S570	S570_SuPR_4_Regular	4	N	Navidad	2023-08-29T19:28:01.204Z	308.079	2406.69	2.527293	-94.075485
S570	S570_SuPR_5_isRNAlater	5	N	Navidad	2023-08-30T06:00:59.928Z	270.385	2399.14	2.527333	-94.075639
S570	S570_SuPR_6_Regular	6	N	Navidad	2023-08-30T08:00:12.858Z	352.255	2396.44	2.527195	-94.076046
S570	S570_SuPR_7_Regular	7	N	Navidad	2023-08-30T08:32:26.804Z	195.156	2395.93	2.527362	-94.076076
S570	S570_SuPR_8_isRNAlater	8	Y	Navidad	2023-08-30T09:35:27.595Z	115.554	2387.49	2.527279	-94.076113
S570	S570_SuPR_9_isRNAlater	9	Y	Navidad	2023-08-30T09:58:36.912Z	87.935	2391.21	2.527256	-94.076117
S570	S570_SuPR_10_isRNAlater	10	Y	Navidad	2023-08-30T10:51:03.902Z	5.268	2404.05	2.527357	-94.07553
S570	S570_SuPR_11_Regular	11	N	Navidad	2023-08-30T11:09:40.065Z	5.477	2403.95	2.527354	-94.075532
S570	S570_SuPR_12_isRNAlater	12	Y	Navidad	2023-08-30T11:57:21.365Z	355.419	2408.27	2.527238	-94.075451
S570	S570_SuPR_13_isRNAlater	13	Y	Navidad	2023-08-30T12:13:40.855Z	355.825	2407.04	2.527239	-94.075444
S570	S570_SuPR_14_isRNAlater	14	Y	Navidad	2023-08-30T12:33:50.065Z	331.458	2404.54	2.527244	-94.075428
S571	S571_SuPR_1_Regular_REAL	1	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-02T06:53:37.792Z	289.012	2475.42	2.531941	-94.359023
S571	S571_SuPR_2_Regular	2	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-01T15:51:45.566Z	83.271	2453.85	2.526539	-94.366992
S571	S571_SuPR_3_Regular	3	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-01T16:26:30.428Z	82.963	2490.34	2.526788	-94.361577
S571	S571_SuPR_4_Regular	4	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-02T07:45:24.947Z	312.072	2475.77	2.531917	-94.358961
S571	S571_SuPR_5_Regular	5	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-02T12:51:47.136Z	181.192	2485.93	2.531753	-94.358634

Dive #	SuPR ID	Filter #	<i>In situ</i> RNA later?	Vent Field	Timestamp	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon
S571	S571_SuPR_6_Regular	6	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-02T13:15:17.433Z	167.146	2476.65	2.53176	-94.358677
S571	S571_SuPR_7_Regular	7	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-02T17:24:20.712Z	323.146	2480.22	2.531749	-94.358751
S572	S572_SuPR_1_Regular	1	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-03T12:41:45.296Z	10.514	2479.45	2.533527	-94.354368
S572	S572_SuPR_2_Regular	2	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-03T19:13:16.197Z	120.394	2476.98	2.531967	-94.359092
S572	S572_SuPR_3_Regular	3	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-03T21:33:01.479Z	23.967	2465.21	2.531952	-94.359017
S572	S572_SuPR_4_Regular	4	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-03T22:34:37.643Z	103.568	2468.17	2.531949	-94.358634
S572	S572_SuPR_5_Regular	5	N	94.4W DSL2b				n/a	n/a
S573	S573_SuPR_1_Regular	1	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-04T09:40:17.860Z	325.887	2467.76	2.531874	-94.358592
S573	S573_SuPR_2_Regular	2	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-04T10:54:27.709Z	288.435	2457.25	2.531941	-94.358528
S573	S573_SuPR_3_Regular	3	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-04T11:21:51.586Z	1.868	2472.2	2.531878	-94.358585
S573	S573_SuPR_4_Regular	4	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-04T13:45:59.950Z	152.869	2466.07	2.532021	-94.358581
S573	S573_SuPR_5_Regular	5	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-04T15:24:58.552Z	5.054	2473.14	2.531872	-94.358589
S573	S573_SuPR_6_Regular	6	N	94.4W DSL2b	2023-09-04T16:57:00.265Z	62.545	2485.91	2.531774	-94.358749
S573	S573_SuPR_7_Regular	7	N	94.4W DSL2b			n/a	n/a	n/a
S575	S575_SuPR_1_Regular	1	N	Iguanas	2023-09-08T02:22:49.625Z	129.457	1645.39	2.10424	-91.925072
S575	S575_SuPR_2_Regular	2	N	Iguanas	2023-09-08T02:39:07.392Z	118.586	1645.2	2.104241	-91.925038

Dive #	SuPR ID	Filter #	<i>In situ</i> RNA later?	Vent Field	Timestamp	Heading	Depth (m)	Lat	Lon
S575	S575_SuPR_3_Regular	3	N	Iguanas	2023-09-08T11:28:59.585Z	271.055	1667.76	2.104001	-91.92635
S575	S575_SuPR_4_Regular	4	N	Iguanas	2023-09-08T10:30:21.577Z	88.55	1667.98	2.10404	-91.926086
S575	S575_SuPR_5_Regular	5	N	Iguanas	2023-09-08T12:08:57.910Z	185.779	1668.38	2.10442	-91.926487
S575	S575_SuPR_6_Regular	6	N	Iguanas	2023-09-08T13:07:29.062Z	179.885	1666.55	2.104169	-91.926491
S575	S575_SuPR_7_Regular	7	N	Iguanas			n/a	n/a	n/a
S575	S575_SuPR_10_Regular	10	N	Iguanas	2023-09-08T03:09:06.816Z	252.328	1646.95	2.104099	-91.925064
S576	S576_SuPR_1_Regular	1	N	Iguanas	2023-09-09T06:55:23.115Z	256.278	1671.06	2.105066	-91.938005
S576	S576_SuPR_2_Regular	2	N	Iguanas	2023-09-09T07:29:08.314Z	69.274	1674.33	2.105062	-91.937885
S576	S576_SuPR_3_Regular	3	N	Iguanas	2023-09-09T08:18:42.097Z	259.063	1672.66	2.105081	-91.93746
S576	S576_SuPR_4_Regular	4	N	Iguanas	2023-09-09T08:49:21.443Z	286.776	1674.95	2.105041	-91.937652
S576	S576_SuPR_5_Regular	5	N	Iguanas	2023-09-09T19:40:57.340Z	194.7	1641.05	2.104801	-91.938047
S576	S576_SuPR_6_Regular	6	N	Iguanas	2023-09-09T20:06:01.892Z	195.068	1643.16	2.104802	-91.938037
S576	S576_SuPR_7_Regular	7	N	Iguanas	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
S576	S576_SuPR_8_Regular	8	N	Iguanas	2023-09-09T20:24:52.306Z	195.397	1642.35	2.104801	-91.938042
S576	S576_SuPR_9_Regular	9	N	Iguanas	2023-09-09T19:14:06.453Z	197.891	1660.52	2.104915	-91.938049
S576	S576_SuPR_12_Regular	12	N	Iguanas	2023-09-09T22:51:28.551Z	2.692	1676.26	2.110567	-91.935854

Table A4: Metadata for sulfide samples collected with ROV *SuBastian*.

*Samples written in gray not sampled by USGS

Dive #	Sample ID	Sample Type	Lat (dd)	Lon (dd)	Water Depth (m)	Date Collected	McDermott Lab	Girguis Lab	SeaLog Description
S0562	R01	RNA Later - High T active chimney	2.1044	-91.936321	1656.18	8/19/2023		x	2023-08-19T11:20:23.889Z
S0562	R02-A	High temperature active chimney	2.104403	-91.936317	1656.21	8/19/2023		R02-B	2023-08-19T11:29:16.965Z
S0562	R03	RNA Later - focused lowT active chimney	2.104405	-91.936296	1656.94	8/19/2023		x	2023-08-19T12:54:27.760Z
S0562	R04	Talus	2.104802	-91.937589	1670.48	8/19/2023			2023-08-19T15:46:09.200Z
S0562	R05	High temperature active chimney	2.104321	-91.936304	1648.22	8/19/2023			2023-08-19T19:30:01.579Z
S0562	R06-A	High temperature active chimney	2.10433	-91.936301	1648.36	8/19/2023	R06-C	R06-B	2023-08-19T19:40:25.833Z
S0562	R07-A	Inactive chimney	2.105069	-91.93782	1672.71	8/19/2023		R07-B	2023-08-19T20:56:10.682Z
S0562	R08-A	Inactive chimney	2.105071	-91.937818	1672.74	8/19/2023		R08-B	2023-08-19T20:58:47.908Z
S0563	R01	RNA Later - High T active chimney	2.104002	-91.926534	1667.75	8/22/2023		x	2023-08-20T18:26:16.819Z
S0563	R02-A	High temperature	2.104941	-91.926273	1643.99	8/22/2023	R02-C	R02-B	2023-08-20T22:06:18.456Z

Dive #	Sample ID	Sample Type	Lat (dd)	Lon (dd)	Water Depth (m)	Date Collected	McDermott Lab	Girguis Lab	SeaLog Description
		active chimney							
S0563	R03-A	High temperature active chimney	2.104943	-91.926278	1644.13	8/22/2023	R03-B		2023-08-20T22:29:08.338Z
S0563	R04	High temperature active chimney	2.104956	-91.926221	1650.15	8/22/2023			2023-08-20T22:50:18.805Z
S0563	R05	Talus	2.104524	-91.926051	1668.9	8/22/2023			2023-08-20T23:37:02.506Z
S0563	R06	Talus	2.104546	-91.92603	1667.95	8/22/2023			2023-08-21T00:00:13.258Z
S0563	R07	Talus	2.104546	-91.926019	1668.21	8/22/2023			2023-08-21T00:36:00.060Z
S0564	R01-A	High temperature active chimney	2.103955	-91.926471	1660.44	8/22/2023	R01-D	R01-C, R01-B (RNA Later)	2023-08-22T02:13:11.539Z
S0564	R02	High temperature active chimney	2.10451	-91.925537	1667.14	8/22/2023			2023-08-22T06:06:20.071Z
S0564	R03-A	High temperature active chimney	2.104885	-91.926239	1648.55	8/22/2023	R03-B		2023-08-22T07:23:53.245Z
S0564	R04	Inactive chimney	2.103304	-91.92665	1659.86	8/22/2023			2023-08-22T11:11:02.899Z
S0564	R05	Talus	2.103465	-91.926706	1666.64	8/22/2023			2023-08-22T11:29:00.117Z

Dive #	Sample ID	Sample Type	Lat (dd)	Lon (dd)	Water Depth (m)	Date Collected	McDermott Lab	Girguis Lab	SeaLog Description
S0574	R01	Talus	2.104376	-91.925646	1666.09	9/6/2023			2023-09-06T06:04:43.841Z
S0575	R01	High temperature active chimney	2.104189	-91.925084	1666.06	9/8/2023	R01-B		2023-09-08T00:37:26.271Z
S0575	R02	Basalt (from SOI lander)	2.103948	-91.926617	1667.23	9/8/2023	x		2023-09-08T02:06:48.397Z
S0575	R03	Talus	2.104184	-91.925101	1669.72	9/8/2023			2023-09-08T05:45:19.571Z
S0575	R04	Talus	2.10445	-91.925628	1665.75	9/8/2023			2023-09-08T07:05:52.404Z
S0575	R05	Talus	2.104503	-91.926088	1668.96	9/8/2023			2023-09-08T09:19:29.928Z
S0576	R01-A	Active High T	2.105024	-91.937802	1673.64	9/9/2023	R01-B		2023-09-09T10:56:44.735Z
S0576	R02	Talus	2.104868	-91.938147	1673.77	9/9/2023			2023-09-09T18:47:46.991Z
S0576	R03	Talus	2.104867	-91.938148	1673.72	9/9/2023			2023-09-09T18:51:20.080Z
S0565	R01	Inactive chimney	2.099103	-91.906413	1659.06	8/23/2023			2023-08-23T07:51:07.023Z
S0565	R02	Inactive chimney	2.099081	-91.906683	1675.78	8/23/2023			2023-08-23T09:20:38.900Z: Starboard IGT crate. crumbled when put in crate"
S0565	R03-A	High temperature active chimney	2.099438	-91.906128	1669.47	8/23/2023	R03-B	R03-C	2023-08-23T10:05:51.969Z
S0565	R04	Inactive chimney	2.099428	-91.90613	1670.4	8/23/2023		R04-B	2023-08-23T11:03:14.875Z

Dive #	Sample ID	Sample Type	Lat (dd)	Lon (dd)	Water Depth (m)	Date Collected	McDermott Lab	Girguis Lab	SeaLog Description
S0565	R05	Talus	2.099421	-91.905189	1665.37	8/23/2023			2023-08-23T18:36:42.775Z
S0565	R06-A	High temperature active chimney	2.099346	-91.906136	1663.28	8/23/2023	R06-B	R06-C	2023-08-23T21:01:23.701Z
S0566	R01-A	Inactive chimney	2.099429	-91.906131	1669.13	8/24/2023		R01-B	2023-08-24T12:31:04.679Z
S0566	R02	RNA Later - Inactive sulfide	2.09943	-91.906138	1669.17	8/24/2023		x	2023-08-24T12:37:57.254Z
S0566	R03	RNA Later - High T active sulfide	2.099428	-91.906138	1669.21	8/24/2023		x	2023-08-24T12:47:06.942Z
S0566	R04	Talus	2.099419	-91.906055	1670.42	8/24/2023			2023-08-24T15:47:11.322Z
S0566	R05-A	High temperature active chimney	2.099292	-91.905472	1670.95	8/24/2023	x	x	2023-08-24T17:20:27.078Z
S0566	R06	Basalt	2.097633	-91.90362	1688.2	8/25/2023	x		2023-08-24T19:37:52.290Z
S0566	R07	Talus from diffuse flow	2.099228	-91.905027	1660.77	8/24/2023		R07-B	2023-08-24T23:15:03.092Z
S0566	R08	Talus	2.099251	-91.905028	1662.5	8/24/2023		-80 for 16S	2023-08-24T23:51:43.763Z
S0568	R01	Inactive chimney	2.527638	-94.075025	2405.92	8/28/2023			2023-08-28T00:30:01.275Z
S0568	R02-A	High temperature active chimney	2.527699	-94.075119	2409.33	8/28/2023	R02-B	R02-C	2023-08-28T01:45:40.168Z

Dive #	Sample ID	Sample Type	Lat (dd)	Lon (dd)	Water Depth (m)	Date Collected	McDermott Lab	Girguis Lab	SeaLog Description
S0568	R03-A	Active Flange	2.527231	-94.075454	2409.23	8/28/2023		R03-B	2023-08-28T01:45:40.168Z
S0568	R04	Active Flange (crumbled in BB)	2.52723	-94.075456	2409.21	8/28/2023			2023-08-28T05:16:14.882Z
S0568	R05-A	Active Flange	2.527229	-94.075455	2409.27	8/28/2023	R05-B	R05-C	2023-08-28T05:25:34.696Z
S0568	R06-A	Inactive Sulfide	2.527233	-94.075456	2409.11	8/28/2023		R06-B	2023-08-28T05:39:23.759Z
S0568	R07-A	High temperature active chimney	2.527231	-94.075461	2409.19	8/28/2023	R07-B		2023-08-28T05:57:24.649Z
S0568	R08-A	Basalt	2.527656	-94.074484	2409.66	8/28/2023	R08-B		2023-08-28T09:05:03.031Z
S0568	R09	Inactive chimney	2.527748	-94.074512	2413.56	8/28/2023			2023-08-28T09:26:57.969Z
S0570	R01	Talus	2.527653	-94.074493	2410.03	8/29/2023			2023-08-29T09:17:14.705Z
S0570	R02	Inactive chimney	2.527753	-94.07469	2415.44	8/29/2023			2023-08-29T09:41:05.981Z
S0570	R03	Basalt	2.527629	-94.074612	2410.02	8/29/2023			2023-08-29T09:50:34.152Z
S0570	R04-A	High temperature active chimney	2.527603	-94.074494	2407.72	8/29/2023		R04-B	2023-08-29T10:33:41.530Z
S0570	R05-A	High temperature active chimney	2.527287	-94.076095	2391.21	8/29/2023	R05-B		2023-08-29T15:08:59.579Z
S0570	R06	Basalt	2.527646	-94.0745	2409.35	8/29/2023			2023-08-30T02:16:58.372Z

Dive #	Sample ID	Sample Type	Lat (dd)	Lon (dd)	Water Depth (m)	Date Collected	McDermott Lab	Girguis Lab	SeaLog Description
S0570	R07	RNA Later - Diffuse flow sulfide	2.527245	-94.075471	2408.7	8/29/2023			2023-08-30T07:44:31.099Z
S0570	R08	RNA Later - High T active chimney	2.527277	-94.076108	2392.64	8/29/2023			2023-08-30T10:22:45.265Z
S0571	R01	Inactive chimney	2.531936	-94.35907	2477.68	9/2/2023			2023-09-02T09:02:19.016Z
S0571	R02	Talus - basalt	2.531916	-94.359079	2480.04	9/2/2023	x		2023-09-02T09:24:45.049Z
S0571	R03	Talus	2.531918	-94.359075	2480.03	9/2/2023			2023-09-02T09:28:40.419Z
S0571	R04	Talus - basalt	2.531895	-94.359065	2481.23	9/2/2023	x		2023-09-02T09:43:32.759Z
S0571	R05	Talus - basalt	2.5319	-94.359066	2481.25	9/2/2023	x		2023-09-02T09:52:30.935Z
S0571	R06	Talus - basalt	2.531894	-94.359066	2481.2	9/2/2023	x		2023-09-02T09:55:19.942Z
S0571	R07	RNA Later - High T active sulfide	2.531705	-94.358612	2487.29	9/2/2023		x	2023-09-02T13:57:28.856Z
S0571	R08-A	Active chimney	2.531721	-94.358657	2486.36	9/2/2023	R08-C	R08-B	2023-09-02T14:55:19.484Z
S0572	R01	Active chimney	2.531934	-94.35907	2477.5	9/3/2023			2023-09-03T17:08:22.761Z
S0573	R01-A	Active chimney	2.531907	-94.358564	2467.98	9/4/2023	R01-B		2023-09-04T10:12:35.140Z
S0573	R02	Inactive chimney	2.531914	-94.358561	2468.28	9/4/2023			2023-09-04T10:34:49.123Z
S0573	R03-A	Active chimney wall	2.531893	-94.358616	2473.44	9/4/2023	R03-B		2023-09-04T14:35:56.316Z

Dive #	Sample ID	Sample Type	Lat (dd)	Lon (dd)	Water Depth (m)	Date Collected	McDermott Lab	Girguis Lab	SeaLog Description
S0573	R04	Oxidized chimney piece	2.531697	-94.358532	2487.49	9/4/2023			2023-09-04T18:31:55.921Z
S0573	R05	Basalt	2.531672	-94.358556	2488.75	9/4/2023			2023-09-04T18:58:50.392Z
S0573	R06	Talus	2.531905	-94.35855	2467.57	9/4/2023			2023-09-04T20:33:42.493Z

*Samples written in gray not sampled by USGS.